

SANSA NEWSLETTER

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IN THIS ISSUE

NEW SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS:

- Two new genera, *Afrotrix* and *Namagelena*, and eighteen new Agelenidae species were added to the SA Spider National list (Haddad *et al.*, 2026) (p. 2).
- More on behaviour of *Myrmarachne* (p. 2) and *Helafricanus fasciatus* (p. 3).
- **NAME CHANGES:** In the Araneidae, *Lipocrea* is synonymised with *Larinia* (Tanikawa *et al.*, 2025) (p. 3).
- New spider genus *Castianeirodes* (Araneae: Corinnidae) (p. 3).

ORBITUARIES: We bade a sad farewell to two former arachnological students, René Fourie and Linde de Jager at the University of the Free State (p. 4), and Piet van Niekerk at the National Collection of Arachnida, who provided assistance with fieldwork (p. 8).

NEW PROJECTS:

- The new SAMBAR FBIP project will focus on three mountain ranges (Cedarberg, Sani Pass and Soutpansberg) in South Africa. Different invertebrate groups will be surveyed, including spiders (p. 5).
- In Angola, a study is underway to compare the spider fauna of relatively undisturbed miombo forests (“pristine” forests) with recently burnt forests (p. 6).

FAMILY REVIEW: Araneidae (pp. 9–16).

QUICK GUIDE: Guide to grass orb-webs (pp. 17–19).

FIRST RECORDS FOR SA: *Cyrtarachne termitophila* Lawrence, 1952 (pp. 20–21) and *Cyrtarachne finniganiae* Lessert, 1936 (p. 22).

SPECIES PAGES: As part of the SANSA species pages series in this issue, we provide more information on two Pholcidae species, *Leptopholcus gracilis* (pp. 23–25) and *Crossopriza lyoni* (pp. 26–27).

SURVEYS:

- **Springbok Flats:** As part of the SANSA surveys of the Waterberg project in the Limpopo Province, we report on a checklist of 245 spider species from 38 families (pp. 28–34) from farms in Springbok Flats sampled during the red quelea project.
- **Meerkat National Park:** As part of SANSA surveys in the South African National Parks, the first checklist of the arachnida of Meerkat National Park is presented, including 87 spider species, 6 scorpion species, 4 Solifugae, and two pseudoscorpions (pp. 35–43).

KEY TO THE FAMILIES AND GENERA OF THE OPILIONES: (pp. 44–49).

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NEW ARTICLE

HADDAD C.R., ZAMANI A & MARUSI Y.M. 2026. West Side Story: systematics of funnel-weavers (Araneae: Agelenidae: Ageleninae) from arid western South Africa, with two new genera and 16 new species. *Zootaxa* 5748 (3): 301–353.

ABSTRACT: In this study, we document the diversity of funnel-weaving spiders (Agelenidae: Ageleninae) in arid western South Africa, a fauna that has historically been understudied. Examination of collected material revealed 16 new species belonging to two tribes, Textricini and Agelenini, representing three genera, including two newly described herein. *Afrotrix* gen. nov. (Textricini) is described to comprise *A. deserticola* (Simon, 1910) comb. nov. (ex. *Benoitia* Lehtinen, 1967), for which a lectotype is newly designated, as well as nine new species: *A. spicula* sp. nov. (type species, M,F), *A. booyeni* sp. nov. (M,F), *A. dejagerae* sp. nov. (M,F), *A. goegap* sp. nov. (F), *A. karoocica* sp. nov. (M,F), *A. lyonsae* sp. nov. (M,F), *A. reginaldi* sp. nov. (M,F), *A. sauria* sp. nov. (F) and *A. tankwa* sp. nov. (M,F). *Benoitia* Lehtinen, 1967 (Agelenini) is represented by the following five new species: *B. arida* sp. nov. (F), *B. leroyae* sp. nov. (F), *B. lunata* sp. nov. (F), *B. meridionalis* sp. nov. (M,F) and *B. namaqua* sp. nov. (M,F). Finally, *Namagelena* gen. nov. (Agelenini) is described to comprise two new species, *N. sola* sp. nov. (type species, M,F) and *N. guttata* sp. nov. (F). A molecular phylogeny is presented based on cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) sequences of 12 species of South African Agelenidae, including 10 described in this paper, which supports the delimitation of the three genera treated. Distribution maps are provided for all the species.

NEW ARTICLE

KELLY M.B.J., DERKARABETIAN S., MCLEAN D.J., SHOFNER R., GRISMADO C.J., HADDAD C.R., CASSIS G., GIRIBET G., MARIE E. HERBERSTEIN M.E. & WOLFF J.O. 2025. Batesian Mimicry Converges toward Inaccuracy in Myrmecomorphic Spiders. *Systematic Biology* 74(6): 967–984. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sysbio/syaf037>

ABSTRACT. Batesian mimicry is an impressive example of convergent evolution driven by predation. However, the observation that many mimics only superficially resemble their models despite strong selective pressures is an apparent paradox. Here, we tested the “perfecting hypothesis”, that posits that inaccurate mimicry may represent a transitional stage at the macroevolutionary scale by performing the hereto largest phylogenetic analysis (in terms of the number of taxa and genetic data) of ant-mimicking spiders across two speciose but independent clades, the jumping spider tribe Myrmarachnini (Salticidae) and the sac spider subfamily Castianeirinae (Corinnidae). We found that accurate ant mimicry evolved in a gradual process in both clades, by an integration of compound traits contributing to the ant-like habitus with each trait evolving at different speeds. Accurate states were highly unstable at the macroevolutionary scale likely because strong expression of some of these traits comes with high fitness costs. Instead, the inferred global optimum of mimicry expression was at an inaccurate state. This result reverses the onus of explanation from inaccurate mimicry to explaining the exceptional evolution and maintenance of accurate mimicry and highlights that the evolution of Batesian mimicry is ruled by multiple conflicting selective pressures.

Figure 1. Traits quantified to determine myrmecomorphy.

NEW ARTICLE

VICKERS M.E., BOOYSEN R. & HADDAD C.R. 2025. Differences in behavioural responses in Intra and Inter sexual Interactions of the sun jumping spider, *Helafricanus fasciatus*, in South Africa. *Journal of Insect Behavior* 38: 30. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10905-025-09894-x>

ABSTRACT. Jumping spiders (Salticidae) are well known for their highly visual and often vibrant displays initiated by males. These displays can occur while males are searching for potential mates and encounter another male (intrasexual), or when males interact with a female (intersexual). While these displays have been widely reported in the literature, the differences between behavioural repertoires for these encounters is still not well understood. Here we described and quantified the repertoire of different behaviour used in intra- and intersexual visual communication (non-aggressive and aggressive) exhibited by males and females during two types of interactions, male-male ($n = 12$) and male-female ($n = 16$), of the sun jumping spider, *Helafricanus fasciatus* Wesolowska, 1986. From the 28 different pairings, we found differences in the types of behaviour exhibited along with the corresponding duration performed by males during male-male and male-female interactions. While in the presence of another male, *H. fasciatus* males exhibited a higher proportion of “display” behaviour as a potential form of assessment of opponent, intimidation and/or threat display, whereas in the presence of females, males were more likely to use “movement” behaviour which

Helafricanus fasciatus male and female Credit: Ruan Booysen

may allow males to capture and retain the attention of females and potentially reduce the distance between spiders. Interestingly, during male-female interactions, males exhibited higher proportions of aggressive behaviour while courting females. For copulation success, neither body size nor body condition correlated with copulations in male-female pairings. We discuss our results in the context of intra- and intersexual interactions and how males may shift their behavioural repertoires depending on the sex.

NEW ARTICLE

TANIKAWA A., INTO T. & PETCHARAD B. 2025. On the synonymization of *Lipocrea* and *Lariniaria* with *Larinia* (Araneae: Araneidae) using molecular systematics. *Acta Arachnologica* 74(2): 85–89. doi: 10.2476/asjaa.74.85

ABSTRACT: Molecular phylogenetic analyses, Bayesian inference and Maximum Likelihood, were conducted using datasets of five genes to assess the validity of the genera *Lipocrea* Thorell 1878 and *Lariniaria* Grasshoff 1970. While the genus *Larinia* Simon 1874 sensu lato was initially suspected to be polyphyletic, the results showed that the target species of this study, including the ones of *Lipocrea* and *Lariniaria*, formed a monophyletic group. Thus, both genera should be considered junior synonyms of *Larinia* as a separation from the latter is unnecessary. Nonetheless, the analysis reaffirmed concerns regarding the potential polyphyly of *Larinia* sensu lato and indicated the need for further investigation

Larinia longissima (Simon, 1881) Credit: Peter Webb

NEW ARTICLE

HADDAD C.R. 2026. On the arboreal Afrotropical ant-mimicking castianeirine spider genus *Castianeirodes* Strand, 1916 (Araneae: Corinnidae). *Zootaxa* 5777(1): 139–154. doi: [10.11646/zootaxa.5777.1.6](https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5777.1.6)

ABSTRACT: The genus *Castianeirodes* Strand, 1916, with *C. insulicola* (Strand, 1916) comb. nov. (ex *Castianeira* Keyserling, 1879) from D.R. Congo as the type species, is revalidated and formally described and diagnosed for the first time. The female holotype of *C. insulicola* is redescribed and illustrated for the first time; the male remains unknown. Three new species are described from both sexes: *C. jocquei* sp. nov. from Ghana, *C. kakamega* sp. nov. from Kenya and *C. natalensis* sp. nov. from South Africa.

Digital microscope photographs of the dorsal habitus of *Castianeirodes natalensis* holotypes from iSimangaliso Wetlands Park, Hell's Gate.

OBITUARIES

FAREWELL TO TWO FORMER ARACHNOLOGICAL STUDENTS

René Fourie (R) and Robin Lyle (L) collecting in coastal forest in southern Mozambique, 2008.

Linde de Jager in the eastern Free State mountains.

In February 2026, we bade a sad farewell to two former arachnological students at the University of the Free State that made meaningful contributions to understanding the biodiversity and ecology of spiders in the Grassland Biome, both of whom passed away after long battles with cancer.

René Fourie studied Entomology from undergraduate to M.Sc level at the university, studying spider ecology in the Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve for her M.Sc. This included several publications on the grassland foliage-dwelling (Fourie *et al.*, 2013) and ground-dwelling spiders (Haddad *et al.*, 2015, 2016). René also revised the African purse-web spiders (Atypidae, *Calommata*) as part of her M.Sc, including the descriptions of three new species, one of which was first collected at Erfenis Dam (Fourie *et al.*, 2011). She presented the results of her work at two AFRAS colloquiums and at the International Congress of Entomology held in South Africa.

Linde de Jager conducted his 3rd year Entomology project on spiders associated with *Searsia lancea* leaf litter in three biotopes at the Free State National Botanical Gardens, which was later published (Haddad *et al.*, 2019), paving the way for further studies of grassland leaf litter assemblages. Although he would continue his post-graduate studies in Botany, he still maintained a keen interest in arthropods, including work as a beekeeper and honey producer.

On behalf of the SANSА community, we extend our condolences to their families and friends. Both will be sorely missed.

REFERENCES

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- FOURIE R., HADDAD C.R. & JOCQUÉ R. 2011. A revision of the purse-web spider genus *Calommata* Lucas, 1837 (Araneae: Atypidae) in the Afrotropical Region. *ZooKeys* 95: 1–28. doi: 10.3897/zookeys.95.745
- HADDAD C.R., BRABEC M., PEKÁR S. & FOURIE R. 2016. Seasonal population dynamics of a specialised termite-eating spider (Araneae: Ammoxenidae) and its prey (Isoptera: Hodotermitidae). *Pedobiologia* 59: 105–110. doi: 10.1016/j.pedobi.2016.03.003
- HADDAD C.R., DE JAGER L. & FOORD S.H. 2019. Habitats and cardinal directions are key variables structuring spider leaf litter assemblages under *Searsia lancea*. *Pedobiologia* 73: 10–19. doi: 10.1016/j.pedobi.2019.01.002
- HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., FOURIE R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2015. Effects of a fast-burning spring fire on the ground-dwelling spider assemblages (Arachnida: Araneae) in a central South African grassland habitat. *African Zoology* 50: 281–292. doi: 10.1080/15627020.2015.1088400

Submitted by Prof Charles Haddad

NEW PROJECT

SAMBAR

SOUTH AFRICAN MOUNTAIN BIODIVERSITY AND RESILIENCE

Three provinces, three mountains, three long-term transects.

Foundational Biodiversity Information Programme (FBIP) - Full Large Grants

Title: SAMBAR: South African Mountain Biodiversity and Resilience

Year of Funding: 2026-01-01 to 2028-12-31

Project leader: Prof. Caswell Munyai (caswell.munyai@gmail.com)

<https://sambar.org.za/>

The South African Mountain Biodiversity and Resilience (SAMBAR) project encompasses three elevational transects that have been sampled for ground-active invertebrates for over 20 years. Long-term biodiversity studies are critical for disentangling the effects of natural population change from other factors, such as climate change. In this sense, the SAMBAR transects are an important resource for southern African biodiversity science.

The project will provide empirical evidence for how species and ecological communities shift along elevational and climate gradients, which is critical for understanding the ecological consequences of climate change. The SAMBAR gradients are unique in South Africa in that they provide the best long-term monitoring of invertebrate populations available in the country. Analysing these temporal patterns is central to answering questions in climate change research and predicting the future state of these ecosystems.

The species inventories will guide conservation priorities in South African montane areas, highlighting species most vulnerable to climate change. The work supports national biodiversity monitoring, the Convention on Biological Diversity, and the Global Biodiversity Framework, particularly Goals A and B. By unifying taxonomic efforts across SAMBAR gradients, the project will improve protected area management by tracking biodiversity shifts across elevation, land use, and climate gradients.

Research to date has focused on understanding how ant (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) diversity changes across elevations and over time, and how these changes depend on the physiological, morphological, and behavioural characteristics of different species. Research on the effects of elevation and time on mountain spider diversity in the Cederberg (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2016) and the Soutpansberg (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al., 2024) has been published, and this will provide a good basis for this project. In storage, we have a wealth of samples from collembola, beetles, and wasps that can shed further light on the elevation and climatic drivers of invertebrate biodiversity.

REFERENCES

FOORD S.H. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2016. The effect of elevation and time on mountain spider diversity: a view of two aspects in the Cederberg mountains of South Africa. *Journal of Biogeography* 3 (12): 2354– 2365.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., MUNYAI T.C., SCHOEMAN C.S., HANN N. & FOORD S.H. 2024. Soutpansberg Mountain: a spider hotspot in the Limpopo Province of South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Invertebrates* 65(2): 85–114.

The **Cederberg transect** (0 – 1900 m a.s.l.), encompassing fynbos and karoo vegetation types, and was sampled biannually from 2002 until 2012 and has recently been re-established and was resampled from October 2022 – March 2025.

The **Maloti-Drakensberg grassland transect at Sani Pass** (900 – 3000 m a.s.l.) was established in 2006 and has been sampled biannually since then, recording its 20th year of sampling in January 2025.

The **Soutpansberg transect** (800 – 1700 m a.s.l.), consisting of bushveld and related vegetation, was established in

STUDY OF ANGOLAN ARACHNIDS GETS A BOOST

Tharina L. Bird

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Angola's biodiversity remains poorly documented, leaving the country a significant white spot on the map for most taxa. This is equally true for arachnids (Bird & Booysen, 2024). However, this situation is beginning to change.

A successful National Geographic/Bird Wildlife Trust expedition to the Lisima Highlands in Angola in October/November 2024 (Bird & Booysen, 2024) sparked renewed interest in arachnids among both Angolan and international researchers, with numerous specimens collected and photographed (Fig. 1). It is, however, the involvement of fifth-year B.Sc. student Laurinda Mandela de Fraga that took arachnid sampling to a new level (Fig. 2). Laurinda, a student at the Agostinho Neto University in Luanda, is using her final-year BSc project to compare relatively undisturbed miombo forests ("pristine" forests) with recently burnt forests, with spiders serving as her indicator organisms. In the remote Lisima Highlands, burning these forests is a common practice, largely carried out to facilitate hunting.

Figure 1. Some spiders recently collected in Angola. a. *Hamataliwa* Keyserling, 1887 sp. (Oxyopidae), b. *Apochinomma* Pavesi, 1881 sp. (Corinnidae), c. *Neoscona rufipalpis* (Lucas, 1858) (Araneidae), d, e. unidentified Ctenidae spp. Photos: a, b: Ruan Booysen; c-e: TLB

Laurinda collected her first set of data in the miombo forests surrounding the village of Tempué in the Lisima Highlands of Angola during April-May 2025. She was joined by Tharina Bird from the DITSONG: National Museum of Natural History (DNMNH) in South Africa, as well as Augusto Sanguende, originally from Tempué. In October 2025, Laurinda returned to the field to complete her data collection, and she is currently finalizing her analysis and write-up.

Arachnids had completely captured Laurinda's heart. During a three-month visit to South Africa in 2025 to start sorting the specimens that she collected, she translated a spider identification key into Portuguese. She also met with Prof. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman (Fig. 3a) whose prolific research helped put South African spiders on the global map.

Figure 2. Student Laurinda de Fraga collecting specimens in the field. a, b. Collecting data for her research project, including preparing transects in the day (a.) and hand collect using eyeshine detection at night (b.), and c, d. general sampling through beating (c.) and sweep netting (d). Photos: a, b: TLB; c, d: Augusto Castro Ndala

Ansie gifted Laurinda three spider books she had authored – a treasured start to Laurinda's personal arachnid library. Back home, Laurinda conducted a fieldtrip to collect scorpions near the Angolan coast. In February 2026, Laurinda herself joined the next National Geographic/Bird Wildlife Trust expedition – this time as the resident arachnologist (Fig. 3b). During the expedition, she collected about 1 200 spider specimens, alongside scorpions and solifuges.

Laurinda plans to continue an MSc in arachnology. With dedication and passion, she is helping to erase the 'white spot' that Angola has long represented on the arachnological map.

Figure 3. Laurinda de Fraga a. receiving some spider books from Prof. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman (left), and b. on the February 2026 National Geographic/Bird Wildlife Trust expedition to the Lisima Highlands in Angola with some other expedition team members. Photos: a. TLB; b. Augusto Castro Ndala

REFERENCE

BIRD T.L. & BOOYSEN R. 2024. Expedition to sample arachnids in Angola. *SANSA Newsletter* 52: 43–44.

Egg laying behaviour of *Loxosceles simillima* Lawrence, 1927 in captivity

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While keeping and breeding *Loxosceles simillima* Lawrence, 1927 in captivity, some interesting observations were made about their behaviour. These observations include the formation of an egg sac and intraspecific tolerance toward other specimens.

An adult female *L. simillima* was kept in a small plastic enclosure measuring 12x12x6 cm, with 1 cm of sand and a few small branches added. One day, I observed the spider building an egg sac and depositing it into the sand. On the photographs it can be seen how the spider first built a crater-like depression and filled it with a layer of silk (Fig. 1). Then she dropped the eggs (Fig. 2) and covered them again with a silk layer (Fig. 3). At the end the crater rims were turned over the inner layer of silk, so the finished egg sac was not visible anymore (Fig. 4). This took the spider several hours.

One month later, the spiderlings hatched from the egg sac and were guarded by the mother. This led to another observation: The mother did not feed on the spiderlings. When small crickets were dropped into the web, the adult spider attacked them and killed them by injecting venom. Then it fed on the insect together with the spiderlings (Figs 5 & 6) and eventually even left the prey for them to feed on while holding herself back. Even when the spiders grow larger, they still keep groups together, as long as there is enough space and food available.

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Figures 1-6. *Loxosceles simillima* female. 1. Female making a crater in the sand. 2. She deposit the eggs. 3. The eggs are covered with a thin silk layer. 4. The crater is covered with silk and sand. 5-6. Female with her spiderlings.

NEW SOUTH AFRICAN PUBLICATIONS

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., WEBB P. & UYS W. 2025. First record of the African wandering spider *Afroneutria erythrochelis* (Simon, 1877) from South Africa (Araneae: Ctenidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 56: 14–16. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18043591>

BOOYSEN R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2025. First records of *Neoscona kisangani* Grasshoff, 1986 from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 56: 17–18. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18043736>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & UYS W. 2025. The red patch crab spider *Thomisus australis* Comellini, 1957 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 56: 20–23. <https://zenodo.org/records/18051863>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & UYS, W. 2025. More on the crab spider *Thomisus stenningi* Pocock, 1900 in South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 56: 24–27. <https://zenodo.org/records/18058252>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A. 2025. Colour variations in *Cyrtophora citricola* (Araneae: Araneidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 56: 13. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18058288>

HADDAD C.R., ZAMANI A. & MARUSI Y.M. 2026. West Side Story: systematics of funnel-weavers (Araneae: Agelenidae: Ageleninae) from arid western South Africa, with two new genera and 16 new species. *Zootaxa* 5748 (3): 301–353.

HADDAD C.R. 2026. On the arboreal Afrotropical ant-mimicking castianeirine spider genus *Castianeirodes* Strand, 1916 (Araneae: Corinnidae). *Zootaxa* 5777(1): 139-154. <https://doi: 10.11646/zootaxa.5777.1.6>

HU C.H., ZHANG H., JIANG M.J. & LIU F.J. 2026. Re-delimitation of the genus *Emertonella* (Araneae, Theridiidae, Hadrotarsinae) and taxonomic notes on *Euryopis* and *Phycosoma* from China. *ZooKeys* 1270: 285-305. <https://doi: 10.3897/zookeys.1270.175743>

KELLY M.B.J., DERKARABETIAN S., MCLEAN D.J., SHOFNER R., GRIS-MADO C.J., HADDAD C.R., CASSIS G., GIRIBET G., MARIE E. HERBER-STEIN M.E. & WOLFF J.O. 2025. Batesian Mimicry Converges toward Inaccuracy in Myrmecomorphic Spiders. *Systematic Biology* 74(6): 967–984. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sysbio/syaf037>

MDAZU S., MUNYAI C. & NIBA A. 2026. Habitat influence on epigeic spider diversity in Silaka, Langeni and Kambi Forests, Eastern Cape, South Africa. *African Journal of Ecology* 64:e70149. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aje.70149>.

MONTANA K.O., CALA-RIQUELME F., CREWS S.C., GORNEAU J.A., AL-JAMAL A.M., ALEQUÍN L.D., SPAGNA J.C., BALLARIN F. & ESPOSITO L.A. 2025. Tailor's drawer no more: a reappraisal of the spider family Dictynidae O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871 sensu lato. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 204(2, zlaf007): 1–97. <https://doi: 10.1093/zoolinlean/zlaf007>

TANIKAWA A., INTO T. & PETCHARAD B. 2025. On the synonymization of *Lipocrea* and *Larinaria* with *Larinia* (Araneae: Araneidae) using molecular systematics. *Acta Arachnologica* 74(2): 85–89. <https://doi: 10.2476/asjaa.74.85>

VICKERS M.E., BOOYSEN R. & HADDAD C.R. 2025. Differences in behavioural responses in Intra and Inter sexual Interactions of the sun jumping spider, *Helaffricanus fascinatius*, in South Africa. *Journal of Insect Behavior* 38: 30. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10905-025-09894-x>

ORBITUARY — PIET VAN NIEKERK

It is with great sadness that we inform you of the passing of one of our colleagues Mr. Piet van Niekerk who worked at Plant Health and Protection: Roodeplaat campus. At the time of his death, he occupied the position of Senior Research Assistant. Mr. van Niekerk served the organization well for 39 years.

During his career, Mr van Niekerk helped and assisted with many different projects and research focus. He started off his career assisting in pesticide analysis work, with a focus on Quelea birds and how to control them. Later assisting with pesticide residue in small mammals and its effects in the environment.

In the last decade, he worked more in plant health where he assisted many of the ARC staff with fieldwork in surveys, product development and agricultural training. Mr. van Niekerk began his journey with spiders during the SANBI Karoo BioGap project and has assisted in various activities relating to the National Collection of Arachnida. He was always willing to assist with a smile, while helping to troubleshoot any problems that might arise. He had a hands-on approach to work and enjoyed working as a team. He enjoyed the outdoor and was always ready with

NEWS FLASHES.....
SOME FALSE NEWS

In SANSA Newsletter 56 (2025): 19, we report that the first record of the zebra spider *Viridasius* Simon, 1889 has been recorded from South Africa (Araneae: Viridasiidae). However, thanks to iNaturalist members who sampled specimens for us, we were able to send material to Rudy Jocqué and Arnaud Henrard for identification. They reported that it is a Ctenidae belonging to the genus *Macroctenus* Henrard & Jocqué, 2017. This relatively new genus is an African endemic represented by five species. However, this new species will be the first from South Africa. Currently we are still need more specimens, especially females.

LATE NEW

Hu *et al.* 2026 provided taxonomic amendments for the theridiid genera *Emertonella* Bryant, 1945, *Euryopis* Menge, 1868, and *Phycosoma* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1880.

New names listed in the WSC for some South African species:

- *Emertonella episinoides* (Walckenaer, 1847) from *Euryopis episinoides* (Walckenaer, 1847)
- *Emertonella funebris* (Hentz, 1850) from *Euryopis funebris* (Hentz, 1850)

A REVIEW OF THE ARANEIDAE GENERA AND SPECIES IN SOUTH AFRICA (ARACHNIDA: ARANEAE)

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ABSTRACT: South Africa has a rich fauna of Araneidae, with 112 species across 40 genera listed on the South African National Spider Species list. Since the publication of the Araneidae Photo Identification Guides, several changes have been published, supported by new distribution records from iNaturalist. However, except for the species that have been confirmed and are listed for South Africa in the World Spider Catalogue, several species remain of uncertain identification or are completely unknown. Updated data show that 22% Araneidae species are South African endemics with 62 species (55.4%) found throughout Africa, and 16 species (4%) have a wide distribution beyond Africa. But several recorded species remain to be identified, and the expected number of Araneidae species could be as high as 140.

Keywords: biodiversity, cosmopolitan, introduced, South African National Survey (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

Biodiversity is one of the most important concepts in contemporary biology, with a broad range of applications. In South Africa, the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) was initiated in 1997 with the primary aim of documenting and describing the arachnid fauna. During the SANSA surveys, large numbers of Araneidae spiders were sampled and need to be identified to address conservation issues. Only a few araneid genera in South Africa have been revised, complicating identification. Some of the revisions were by Emerit (1973), who revised the Gasteracanthinae of South Africa; Grasshoff (1984), who revised *Caerostris* and *Neoscona* (Grasshoff, 1986); and Bjørn (1997), who revised the *Argiope* species.

Pycnacantha tribulus (Fabricius, 1781) was the first Araneidae species described from South Africa more than 240 years ago (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024). Since then, numerous species have been added to the species list.

- In 2010, in the first Spider Atlas of South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010), 101 Araneidae species from 38 genera were listed with distribution maps.
- In 2022, in the three Araneidae Photo Identification Guides (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022 a-c), 105 species were discussed.
- In 2023, with the publication of the first checklist of spiders of South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023), 100 species were listed. Five *Araneus* species described by Strand (1907, 1909) were listed as nomen dubium in the World Spider Catalog (2026) and subsequently removed from the list (Nentwig *et al.*, 2019).
- In the 2026 Spider National list, as well as the World Spider Catalog (2026) for South Africa, there are 112 araneid species listed. The increased species numbers were due to the discovery of species known from Africa also occurring in South Africa (Table 2). However, there are still about eight species recorded from South Africa but of which the identity still need to be confirm (see pp. 12-13) as well as 13 unknown species (p.14).

ARANEIDAE: SOUTH AFRICAN ENDEMIC SPECIES

In Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2010), 26 Araneidae species were listed as endemic to South Africa. Thirteen of these endemic species were described between 1781 and 1907, only with brief descriptions and no drawings, complicating identification.

Five of the species were described by Simon (1895, 1897, 1903), and four of them were recollected and redescribed (Table 1). However, of the old species, there are still two: *Nemospiza conspiciata* Simon, 1903 and *Araneus graemii* Pocock, 1900, which have not been recollected. The five species of Strand (1907, 1909) were listed as nomen dubium (Nentwig *et al.*, 2019) and removed from the list, resulting in the number of endemic species declining to 20 as listed in Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2023).

Based on iNaturalist records, there are now only 16 species on the South African endemic list (Table 1). Species like *Araneus coccinella* Pocock, 1898; *Cladomelea akermani* Hewitt, 1923; *Nemoscolus elongatus* Lawrence, 1947; *Pycnacantha tribulus* (Fabricius, 1781) and *Singa albidorsata* Kauri, 1950 have a wider distribution as South Africa.

TABLE 1. List of 16 Araneidae species that are endemic to South Africa with references for further reading.

SPECIES	FURTHER READING
<i>Araneus graemii</i> Pocock, 1900	WSC not recollected
<i>Araneus haploscapellus</i> (Strand, 1907)	Listed as nomen dubium but recollected
<i>Araneus varus</i> (Kauri, 1950)	Marusik (2017); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Caerostris tinamaze</i> Gregorič, 2015	Gregorič <i>et al.</i> (2015); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Cladomelea debeeri</i> Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2004	Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2004); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Gastroxya benoiti</i> Emerit, 1973	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b)
<i>Ideocaira transversa</i> Simon, 1903	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb (2024).
<i>Ideocaira triquetra</i> Simon, 1903	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b)
<i>Isoxya yatesi</i> Emerit, 1973	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2025)
<i>Larinia natalensis</i> (Grasshoff, 1971)	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b)
<i>Nemoscolus obscurus</i> Simon, 1897	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022c)
<i>Nemospiza conspiciata</i> Simon, 1903	WSC not recollected
<i>Paralarinia bartelsi</i> (Lessert, 1933)	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022c)
<i>Pasilobus dippenaarae</i> Roff & Haddad, 2015	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022c); Roff & Haddad (2015)
<i>Singafrotypa mandela</i> Kuntner & Hormiga, 2002	Kuntner & Hormiga (2002); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022c)
<i>Ursa turbinata</i> Simon, 1895	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022c)

ARANEIDAE: AFRICAN ENDEMIC SPECIES

Presently, 62 species (55.4%) are recorded throughout Africa frequently outside its type locality (Table 2). Araneidae spiders, especially juveniles and small-bodied species, use ballooning to travel across grasslands, savannas, deserts, and forests. Ballooning allows spiders to cross long stretches of open plains where walking would be inefficient. This is especially important in Africa, where habitats can be widely spaced and are frequently disturbed by fire, grazing, or seasonal flooding. Spiders also use electric fields to launch even when winds are calm, common during early morning or storm-related atmospheric changes.

Africa’s wet–dry seasons create cycles of resource abundance and scarcity. It enables spiders to move between isolated patches of suitable habitat, promoting genetic mixing and recolonisation after environmental stress.

Africa’s natural disturbance cycles help drive spider dispersal. Frequent fires in savannas and grasslands clear vegetation. Spiders then recolonize rapidly by ballooning, repopulating burned areas. Similar behaviour is noted globally, including mass aerial escapes during disasters.

TABLE 2. Araneidae species endemic to Africa that has also recorded from South Africa since 2020. Distribution data from the World Spider Catalog.

SPECIES	DISTRIBUTION	FURTHER READING
1. <i>Acantharachne seydeli</i> Giltay, 1935	Congo (DRC), South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022e)
2. <i>Aethriscus olivaceus</i> Pocock, 1902	Congo (DRC), South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
3. <i>Acusilas africanus</i> Simon, 1895	Cameroon, Congo (DRC), Gabon, Sierra Leone, Tanzania, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
4. <i>Afracantha camerunensis</i> (Thorell, 1899)	Cameroon, Congo (DRC), Ghana, Swaziland, Botswana, Zambia, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021b)
5. <i>Arachnura scorpionoides</i> Vinson, 1863	Congo (DRC), Ethiopia, Madagascar, Mauritius, Seychelles, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020a)
6. <i>Araneus holzapfelae</i> Lessert, 1936	Mozambique, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord (2020)
7. <i>Araneus tatianea</i> Lessert, 1938	Congo (DRC), South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
8. <i>Argiope tapinobata</i> Bjørn, 1997	Senegal, Namibia, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
9. <i>Bijoaaraneus legonensis</i> (Grasshoff & Edmunds, 1979)	Ghana, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022d)
10. <i>Cladomelea longipes</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877)	Cameroon, Congo (DRC), Zimbabwe, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord (2019)
12. <i>Cyrtarachne finniganae</i> Lessert, 1936	Mozambique, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman (2026)
13. <i>Cyrtarachne termitophila</i> Lawrence, 1952	Congo (DRC), South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman (2026)
14. <i>Cyrtophora petersi</i> Karsch, 1878	Mozambique, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
15. <i>Hypsacantha crucimaculata</i> (Dahl, 1914)	Congo (DRC), Mozambique, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b)
16. <i>Isoxya mossamedensis</i> Benoit, 1962	Angola, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b)
17. <i>Isoxya mucronata</i> Walckenaer, 1841	Congo (DRC), South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b)
18. <i>Mahemba hewitti</i> (Lessert, 1930)	Congo (DRC), South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b)
19. <i>Neoscona kisangani</i> Grasshoff, 1986	Congo (DRC), South Africa	Booyesen & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2025)
20. <i>Paraplectana thorn-toni</i> (Blackwall, 1865)	Mozambique, South Africa	Du Preez & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2022)
21. <i>Poltys monstrosus</i> Simon, 1897	Mozambique, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Uys (2025)

Araneus tatianea

Isoxya mucronata

Poltys monstrosus

Bijoaaraneus legonensis

Araneus holzapfelae

Mahemba hewitti

ARANEIDAE: COSMOPOLITAN AND INTRODUCED SPECIES

Sixteen Araneidae species recorded from South Africa have a distribution range that extends beyond Africa (Table 3). This includes species with a broad natural range as well as those that have expanded through human activity. Introduced species, also called aliens, non-native, exotic, or foreign species, are species that arrive in a new area through deliberate or accidental human transport, rather than through natural dispersal.

Many of these species are regarded as naturalised when they are non-native to an area but have established self-sustaining populations that survive, reproduce, and spread without ongoing human assistance. When their geographic range extends across most or all regions of the world, they are known as cosmopolitan species.

TABLE 3. Araneidae species that have a wider distribution beyond Africa that was possibly introduced into South Africa. Distribution data from the World Spider Catalog.

SPECIES	DISTRIBUTION	FUTHER READING
1. <i>Argiope lobata</i> (Pallas, 1772)	Southern Europe to Central Asia and China, Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
2. <i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	North, Central and South America. Introduced to St. Helena, Africa, Portugal to Israel	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
3. <i>Cyclosa conica</i> (Pallas, 1772)	America, Europe, Turkey, Caucasus, Russia, Europe to Far East, Iran, Central Asia, China. Introduced to South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Zyl (2023)
4. <i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	Mediterranean to Japan, India to Papua New Guinea, Australia. Introduced to St. Helena, South Africa, Eswatini	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
5. <i>Cyclosa oculata</i> (Walckenaer, 1802)	Europe to Far East, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, China. Introduced to South Africa, Hawaii	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
6. <i>Cyrtarachne ixoides</i> (Simon, 1870)	Mediterranean, Caucasus, South Africa, Madagascar	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones (2008)
7. <i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	Widespread in subtropical and tropical areas of Asia, Africa, Australia, and in the warm coastal Mediterranean areas of Europe	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2025)
8. <i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	Pakistan, India, Thailand, China, Taiwan, Philippines, Indonesia. Introduced to South Africa, Eswatini	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021a)
9. <i>Hyposinga pygmaea</i> (Sundevall, 1831)	North America, Europe, Turkey, Israel, Caucasus, Russia (Europe to Far East), Iran, Central Asia, China, Korea, Japan. Introduced to South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021b)
10. <i>Larinia chloris</i> (Audouin, 1826)	Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Turkey, North and East Africa to Israel, Iraq, Iran, India, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh. Introduced to Mozambique, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021b)
11. <i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	Widespread throughout Africa. Introduced to the Caribbean, Colombia, Venezuela to Argentina	Jones & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2022a)
12. <i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	Southern Europe, St. Helena, Africa, Turkey, Middle East, Ukraine, Caucasus, Russia (Europe) to Central Asia	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021c)
13. <i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	Cape Verde, Africa to India	Jones & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2022b)
14. <i>Neoscona vigilans</i> (Blackwall, 1865)	Widespread throughout Africa to the Philippines and New Guinea	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021c)
15. <i>Nephilingis cruentata</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Tropical South America, tropical and subtropical Africa, Indian Ocean Islands, Asia, Australia	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021c)
16. <i>Pararaneus spectator</i> (Karsch, 1885)	East, Central, and South Africa; Yemen; Sinai (Egypt) and Israel	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021c)

Cyrtarachne ixoides

Cyclosa conica

Eriovixia excelsa

Hyposinga pygmaea

Cyclosa oculata

ARANEID SPECIES AND GENERA OBSERVED IN SOUTH AFRICA BUT STILL UNNAMED

The Araneidae is one of the spider families that are very frequently seen in the field and even in gardens. Especially on iNaturalist, they are frequently photographed, but without examination of the genitalia, the specimens are frequently impossible to identify to species level.

From the literature, especially the work of Dr Levi, we have found some look-alikes. We hope that showing all these images will help with species recognition or even encourage people to collect specimens. Presently, we only suggest preliminary generic and species-level identification, which still needs to be confirmed.

- **Cf *Araneus haploscapellus* (Strand, 1907)?**

WAKEFIELD KZN

UMHLANGA

- **Cf *Araneus detrimentosus* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1889)?**

After Levi (1973)

WOODBUSH

JEFFREYSBAY

- **Cf *Araneus partitus* (Walckenaer, 1841)?**

After Levi (1973)

IRENE

- **Cf *Molinaranea phaethontis* (Simon, 1896)?**

Female from Gondwana Private Game Reserve. Credit: Jolandi Buck.

• **ACANTHEPEIRA Marx, 1883?**

After Levi (1976)

ASD

Peter Webb

LEKGALAMEETSE NR

Linda Wiese

• **CHORIZOPEOIDES Mi & Wang, 2018?**

Chorizopesoides orientalis After Mi & Wang (2018).

SOUTPANSBERG

ASD

Wynand Uys

HOEDSPRUIT

• **ZYGIELLA F.O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1902**

After Levi (1972)

Linda Wiese

Linda Wiese

JEFFREYSBAY

• **LARINIOIDES Caporiacco, 1934**

After Levi (1974)

Peter Webb

UMHLANGA

Linda Wiese

THYSPUNT

UNKNOWN SPECIES

CONCLUSION

Except for the species shown here, we have already identified new species within known genera, such as *Cyphalonotus*, *Gea*, *Ideocaira*, *Paraplectana*, *Pycnacantha*, and *Singa*. We will probably eventually have 140 or more species, many more than the 112 currently listed on the South African National Spider Species list. But we need taxonomists and specimens in collections.

But what to do in the meantime? On iNaturalist, these unknowns can maybe be listed under the genera as suggested here. At least if the identification problems are solved, the species distribution records are available.

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Quick guide to the grass long bodied orb-web spiders (Araneae: Araneidae) in South Africa

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Plant-living spiders have a range of characteristic adaptations that facilitate a life on and under bark, in grass, on flowers, among foliage or on sea. As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), all available information on spider species distribution in the South African Grassland Biome was compiled until the end of 2011 and 58 families, 275 genera and 792 described species have been recorded (Haddad *et al.*, 2013).

Grass dwellers are easily recognised by their elongated bodies and long, thin legs. They vary in colour from green to fawn and many are cryptically coloured with stripes along their length, imitating the veins in a blade of grass. They are especially difficult to detect while at rest, when the legs are held forward and parallel with the body. Grass dwellers typically tie twisted grass blades and grass seeds together with their silk threads to create a retreat or to deposit their egg sac (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023).

Kilima decens (Blackwall, 1866)

Epigyne after Grasshoff (1970)

Larinia bifida Tullgren, 1910

After Grasshoff (1970)

Larinia chloris (Audouin, 1826)

After Grasshoff (1970)

***Larinia longissima* (Simon, 1881) (preciously *Lipocrea*)**

***Larinia natalensis* (Grasshoff, 1971)**

***Mahemba hewitti* (Lessert, 1930)**

***Neoscona moreli* (Vinson, 1863)**

***Paralarinia bartelsi* (Lessert, 1933)**

Peter Webb

Peter Webb

After Grasshoff (1970)

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First records of *Cyrtarachne termitophila* Lawrence, 1952 from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: The male of *Cyrtarachne termitophila* Lawrence, 1952, was described from the Democratic Republic of the Congo and is here reported for the first time from South Africa. The general morphology of the species is discussed with notes on its distribution and lifestyle. The female is still unknown.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

Cyrtarachne Thorell, 1868, belongs to the family Araneidae and currently includes more than 57 described species distributed across Africa, Asia, and parts of Oceania. It is a remarkable genus of orb-weaver spiders known for their unusual “spanning thread” webs and bird-dropping mimicry. *Cyrtarachne* is listed in the sub-family Cyrtarachninae, which includes the bolas spiders *Cladomelea* as well as the triangle-web spider *Pasilobus*.

The “spanning thread webs” they construct (Stowe, 1986) are a basic orb-web, but the web diameter, sticky spiral spacing and viscid thread diameter differ from those of the usual orb-webs. The viscid threads are studded with large droplets, which are very effective at catching prey. Each short thread between the radii is known as a spanning thread and is unique in that it breaks when prey contacts it. The prey flies into the web, gets stuck to a viscid thread, the thread breaks, and the spider pulls the prey up to the centre of the web to feed (Tanikawa *et al.*, 2014).

Research in Japan by Cartan & Miyashita (2008) found that the breaking strength, stickiness, thread diameter, and droplet diameter differ significantly from those of other members of Araneidae. They found that the viscid thread diameter was 4x and the breaking strength 7-10x stronger in *Cyrtarachne* than that of other araneids. Like bolas spiders, the adhesiveness of the viscid threads decreases to zero within a few hours. During the day, the spider rests on close-by vegetation mimicking bird droppings. Of the eight species of *Cyrtarachne* known from Africa, only one, *C. ixoides* (Simon, 1870), has so far been reported from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones, 2008).

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) large numbers of Araneidae were sampled and photographed (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Also have several known species from Africa added to the South Africa National Spider List (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). This include several Araneidae species such as *Cyrtarachne termitophila* that are here the first time recorded from South Africa.

TAXONOMY

Cyrtarachne termitophila Lawrence, 1952

Cyrtarachne termitophila Lawrence, 1952: 10 (M)

Diagnostic characters: Male. TL 2 mm. Carapace orange, darker around border (Fig. 1); as wide as long, narrower in eye region (Figs 1 & 5); with three large setae; a small seta posterior of posterior median eyes; two medially on both sides of fovea; setae sometimes lost; anterior eye row viewed from the front strongly recurved; anterior median eyes larger than the posterior median eyes, their own diameter apart; posterior row recurved; lateral eyes closely grouped (Figs 1 & 5).

Figure 1–4. *Cyrtarachne termitophila* male from Isandlwane Nature Reserve. 1. Dorsal view. 2. Ventral view. 3. Male palp. 4. Setae on the front legs. Credit: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Sternum heart-shaped (Fig. 2). Abdomen wider than long, oval; dorsal scute orange; covered with chitinous scute bordered at margin with numerous conical tubercles bearing strong black setae, some lost; sigilla indistinct in male (Figs 1 & 5) but more distinct in juvenile (Figs 9-11); abdomen ventrally with darker tint (Fig. 10). Leg I with stiff setae; tibia I in basal third on inner side with a long spine-like seta directed inwards almost at right angle to the segment (Figs 1,4 &5); Leg 1 with rows of short spinelike setae (Figs 1 & 8). Male palp large as seen from below (Figs 2–3, 6–7). Female unknown.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: DRC, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Isandlwane Nature Reserve, Dundee (-28.86, 28.21). *Limpopo:* Legalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.19, 30.33).

Known distribution of *Cyrtarachne termitophila* in South Africa.

LIFESTYLE

The holotype male was sampled by Mr N. Leleup in 1949 from a termite nest in the DRC. Lawrence (1952) remarked that it is unusual for an Araneidae spider to be found in a termite nest.

The specimens in South Africa were sampled by sweeping grass in two reserves. *Cyrtarachne* species are known to construct “spanning thread webs” usually in low vegetation (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones, 2008). The male with its spikey abdomen blends in with the grasses and is therefore not easily seen.

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Figure 5–8. *Cyrtarachne termitophila* male. 5. Habitus dorsal view. 6–7. Male palp. 8. Leg I. Credits: After Lawrence (1952).

Figure 9–11. *Cyrtarachne termitophila* immature female from Legalameetse Nature Reserve. 9. Dorsal view. 10. Ventral view. 11. Lateral view. Credit: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

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The first record of *Cyrtarachne finniganae* Lessert, 1936 from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: The male of *Cyrtarachne finniganae* Lessert, 1936, was described from Mozambique and is here reported for the first time from South Africa. The female is still unknown. The general morphology of the male is discussed with notes on their distribution and lifestyle.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), large numbers of Araneidae were sampled and photographed. In Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. (2023), a list of 120 Araneidae species have been listed on the South Africa National Spider List, including a single *Cyrtarachne* species. Since then, *C. termitophila* Lawrence, 1952, have been added to the list, and here *C. finniganae* Lessert, 1936 are recorded for the first time from South Africa.

The female is unknown, and the male is small and recognised by the wedge-shaped abdomen, the front legs metatarsi armed internally with numerous erect, spiniform setae arranged in a single row.

TAXONOMY

Cyrtarachne finniganae Lessert, 1936
Cyrtarachne finniganae Lessert, 1936

Diagnostic characters: Male 3 mm. Carapace as wide as long (Figs 1 & 3); narrower in eye region (Figs 1 & 6); anterior eye row viewed from the front strongly recurved; anterior median eyes larger than the posterior median eyes, their own diameter apart; posterior row recurved; lateral eyes closely grouped; sternum heart-shaped (Fig. 2). Abdomen large, broader than long, anteriorly sinuously arched; at the apex broadly rounded, yellowish, with black dorsal area darker; on sides two small, blunt, slightly raised and shining tubercles (Figs 1, 3, 6). Leg 1 with rows of short spinelike setae (Fig. 3). Male palp large as seen from below (Figs 4–5, 7). Female unknown.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA:

Gauteng: Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.71, 28.94). **Limpopo:** Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.19, 30.33).

LIFESTYLE

Cyrtarachne species are known to construct “spanning thread webs” usually in low vegetation (Cartan & Miyashita, 2008). The specimens reported on here were sampled by sweeping grass in two reserves.

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Figures 1–7. *Cyrtarachne finniganae* 1–2. Habitus of juvenile from Ezemvelo Nature Reserve. 3. Line drawing male habitus. 4–5. Male palp. 6. Male from Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve. 7. Male palp. Credits: 3–5. After Lessert (1936); 1–2 and 6–7. A.S. Dippenaar–Schoeman.

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Notes on *Leptopholcus gracilis* Berland, 1920 a leaf-dwelling spider from South Africa (Araneae: Pholcidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Leptopholcus gracilis* Berland, 1920 is a slender, long-legged pholcid spider found across eastern and southern Africa. It's a delicate, cryptic species with very few confirmed observations. It is relatively rare in collections, probably due mainly to its cryptic habits. In this paper, the general morphology is discussed with notes on their lifestyle, conservation and distribution in South Africa.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, iNaturalist, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Leptopholcus* Simon, 1893, represented by 22 species, is known from Africa and Asia. The six African species occur widely in sub-Saharan Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2026). Only one species, *Leptopholcus gracilis*, recorded from South Africa, was first described by Berland in 1920. It is found across East and Southern Africa, specifically in Somalia, Kenya, Tanzania, Mozambique and South Africa. They are pale pholcids with long abdomens and long, thin legs (Figs 1–3). They are known for their leaf-dwelling adaptations. Most species appear to be restricted to relatively humid areas, where they live cryptically on large leaves. Huber (2011), in his revision of some taxa of the Pholcidae examined specimens from Mozambique and South Africa, but only assigned them tentatively to *L. gracilis*.

In this paper, the general morphology is discussed with notes on their lifestyle, conservation and distribution in South Africa.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida, 12 specimens have so far been collected during surveys in Limpopo and KwaZulu-Natal (Fig. 13), and voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria (NCA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al., 2015).

Five additional records, mainly from KwaZulu-Natal, were obtained from research-grade observations by the public available on the iNaturalist database (Fig. 13).

TAXONOMY

Leptopholcus gracilis Berland, 1920

Leptopholcus gracilis Berland, 1920: 131 (f); Brignoli, 1980: 649 (f, Dm); Huber, 2011: 71 (mf); Dippenaar-Schoeman 2023: 106 (f).

Diagnostic characters: TL 6–7 mm. Carapace low, flattened, lacking a fovea (Fig. 2); six eyes in two widely separated triads on the margin of the carapace; anterior median eyes represented as a pair of specks between triads (Figs 2, 5–6). Carapace translucent with dark patches over the eye region (Figs 1–2). Abdomen vermiform; much longer than wide; parallel-sided; anteriorly nearly square, with round posterior margin (Figs 1–3, 7); dorsum pale green to yellowish to almost translucent; decorated with brown paired spots (Fig. 10). Legs are very long; same colour as carapace; distal tips of leg segments darkened; in some femora spotted (Fig. 12); legs without spines and curved hairs.

Figures 1–4. *Leptopholcus gracilis* female from Umhlanga, KwaZulu-Natal. Credit: Peter Webb.

Figures 5–9. *Leptopholcus gracilis*. 5–6. Eye pattern. 7. Habitus lateral view. 8. Epigyne. 9. Palp. Credits: 5–6. After Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué(1997). 8–9. After Huber(2011).

Sexual dimorphism is slight. For epigyne, see Fig. 8; for male palp, see Fig. 9 (Huber, 2011). Sexual dimorphism slight (Huber, 2011).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Somalia, Kenya, Tanzania, Mozambique, Congo, São Tomé and Príncipe, Bandrélé, Mayotte Reunion, Madagascar, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA:

SANSA RECORDS (Fig. 13): KwaZulu-Natal: Bonamanzi Reserve (-32.3, 28.07); Dukuduku State Forest, Hlabisa (-28.37, 32.23); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); iSimangaliso Wetland park, Hells Gate (-28.01, 32.44); iSimangaliso Wetland park, False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); iSimangaliso Wetland park, Kosi Bay Nature(-26.93, 32.87); Ndumo Camp Pongola River (-26.88, 32.25); Tembe Elephant Park, Sihangwana (-27.03, 32.42); Umhlanga Rocks (-29.73, 31.07). **Limpopo:** Klein Kariba (-24.88, 28.29); Kruger National Park, Pafuri (-22.46, 31.3); Rochdale farm (N slopes of Soutpansberg Mts.) (-22.54, 29.41).

INATURALIST OBSERVATIONS (Fig. 13): KwaZulu-Natal: Simangaliso Wetland Park, Emangusi (-27.41, 32.69); uMkhanyakude District (-27.90, 32.35); Paradise Valley, Pinetown(-29.83, 30.89); Tyburn Way, Westville (-29.85, 30.92); KwaMazabane (-26.95, 32.82).

Figures 10–12. *Leptopholcus gracilis*. 10. Female from Umhlanga, KZN showing the long legs. 11. Male from Westville, KZN. 12. Female with spiderlings. Credits: 10. Peter Webb. 11. Suncana Bradley. 12. Nicky Bay.

Figure 13. Map showing the distribution of *Leptopholcus gracilis* from SANSA records in the NCA (red) and research grade observations in iNaturalist (green) downloaded on 15/3/2026. Credit: Wynand Uys

HABITAT

Leptopholcus gracilis is relatively rare in collections, likely due to its cryptic habits. They appear to be restricted to relatively humid areas, as found in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. They were mainly recorded from the Indian Coastal Belt with a few records from the Savanna Biomes (Fig. 13).

LIFESTYLE

They are cryptic leaf-dwelling spiders and live on the underside of large leaves where they spend their resting period most of the day pressed flat against the leaf surface, possibly to avoid predation (Figs 4 & 11). They hunt small arthropods and, with limited vision, they seem to rely on vibrations more than sight. No silk threads are visible in the photographs, so minimal silk is apparently used. Females build elongated egg sacs and with it in their chelicerae stay on the leaf surface on the underside.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has a wide distribution throughout Africa and Madagascar and therefore listed as least concern. In South Africa it has been collected from several protected areas in KwaZulu-Natal such as Hluhluwe Nature Reserve, Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006) and Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2010) and in Limpopo in the Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy, 2003) and the Soutpansberg Mountain (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

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Present status of *Crossopriza lyoni* (Blackwall, 1867) in South Africa (Araneae: Pholcidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Crossopriza lyoni* (Blackwall, 1867) is a widespread, pantropical spider known for its very long legs, squarish abdomen, and close association with human structures. It is harmless to humans and often considered beneficial because it preys on mosquitoes and other small arthropods. The original range of *C. lyoni* is unknown and they have been introduced into different parts of the world accidentally and are now pantropical in distribution. It was the first time reported from South Africa in 2009 from the Tshwane Market where they were regarded as a problem due to the large amounts of unsightly webs they construct on the walls. The presented status and distribution in South Africa is discussed, with notes on the general morphology and notes on their lifestyle.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), cosmopolitan

INTRODUCTION

In 2009, the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) Spider Identification Services received queries from the Tshwane fresh produce market in Gauteng about a spider invasion causing problems. On inspection, we found clusters of unsightly webbing in the corners of the walls and ceiling (Figs 3 & 4). Spiders were present in large numbers in unsightly webs on the walls in most of the halls at the market. The webbing collects dust and dirt, and at a high cost, it is removed annually, but without long-term success. The control was unsuccessful mainly because the spiders escaped by dropping to the ground when anything touched their webs.

Specimens sampled were identified as a Pholcidae species *Crossopriza lyoni* (Blackwall, 1867) (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009). The species has a widespread, pantropical distribution throughout the warmer parts of the world (Huber, 2022) and is recognised by its long legs, rectangular abdomen, and close association with human structures (Figs 1 & 2).

TAXONOMY

The genus *Crossopriza* (Simon, 1893) comprises 24 species (World Spider Catalog, 2026), of which five are recorded from Africa. It has ecological requirements similar to those of *Smeringopus*, but while the latter occurs in Southern and Eastern Africa, *Crossopriza* (5 species in Africa) is restricted to Northern Africa, with additional species on the Arabian Peninsula.

Crossopriza lyoni (Blackwall, 1867) has the widest distribution in Africa, but it also seems to be restricted to the north (Huber, 2005; Huber *et al.*, 1999). The species has a long synonymy list due to historical reclassification and is presently listed in the World Spider Catalog (2026) as probably native to Africa and/or Asia and introduced to several countries.

Diagnostic characters: Small to medium-sized. Carapace with a deep, round depression between the head and thorax, with a distinct pattern; eyes eight, occupying entire width of carapace; anterior median eyes smallest, with other eyes in two triads (Fig. 7). Abdomen high with a triangular appearance in lateral view, with caudal end tapering to a point above spinnerets; marked with a dark, irregular pattern (Figs 5 & 6). Legs thin and much longer than the body (often 8–10 times body length); often with faint dark bands or lines near the joints long (Figs 2 & 6). Females have an epigyne with a flat chitin plate without a movable ligula (Fig. 10). Male palp (Figs 8 & 9).

Figures 1–4. *Crossopriza lyoni*. 1. Female with egg sac. 2. Female collected at the Tshwane market. 3–4. Webbing causing the problems at the market. Credits: 1. Vida vd Walt and 2–4. Les Oates.

Figures 5–10. *Crossopriza lyoni*. 5. Abdomen lateral view. 6. Showing abdomen and long legs. 7. Eye pattern. 8–9. Male palp. 10. Epigyne. Credits: 5–8. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 9–10. After Huber (2022).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Probably native to Africa and/or Asia. Introduced to the Americas, Belgium, Germany, Australia, Micronesia.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: The report on the species sampled in Tshwane (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009) was the first record of the species from South Africa. But observations presently available on iNaturalist (2018-2026) show that the species has a wider distribution in South Africa and was observed in the Limpopo, Mpumalanga, and Western Cape provinces (Fig. 11). Research-grade observations were mainly from records in and around the Kruger National Park, as well as in the Soutpansberg. Only three observations are from the Western Cape (Fig. 11).

From iNaturalist the species seems to occur also observed in other southern African countries such as Botswana, Namibia, Mozambique and Zimbabwe.

Figure 11. Map showing the distribution of *Crossopriza lyoni* research grade observations on iNaturalist (green) downloaded on 15/3/2026. Credit: Wynand Uys.

LIFESTYLE

The species lives in space-webs found in a variety of habitats that are usually dark and shady, such as caves, holes, and crevices. However, *C. lyoni* was found in South Africa in and around buildings such as garages or storerooms. Their webs are made of non-sticky silk and often appears irregular and looks untidy, and loose (Figs 3 & 4). The spider hangs upside-down underneath the more dense part of the web. When disturbed, the spider vibrates it rapidly and was seen dropping to the ground. The eggs (40-50) are formed into a ball are held together by a few silken threads and are carried in the chelicerae of the female (Fig. 1).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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Spider diversity of the Springbok Flats in the Limpopo Province of South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT: SANSA participates in several national research projects. One such project by the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) took place on the Springbok Flats in the Limpopo Province, where methods to control the Red-billed Quelea (*Quelea quelea*) were examined. The Springbok Flats is an extensive plain of fertile thornveld–grassland situated in the Waterberg District of the Limpopo. Surveys to sample invertebrates were conducted on six farms over 27 months, from January 2001 to March 2003. The spiders sampled were sorted and identified at the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection. A total of 245 species and 157 genera from 38 families were recorded. The spiders sampled across the Springbok Flats are part of the SANSA Limpopo survey project and represent 27% of Limpopo spiders and 40% of the Waterberg survey.

Keywords: biodiversity, Savanna Biome, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA).

INTRODUCTION

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), surveys were undertaken throughout the Limpopo Province. One such project was undertaken by the Agricultural Research Council on the Springbok Flats in the Limpopo Province as part of research into controlling red-billed Quelea (*Quelea quelea*). In South Africa, the control of the red-billed quelea is formally organised and government-led, with support from research bodies, farmers, and environmental regulators. Quelea control is implemented at the provincial level, especially in high-risk provinces such as Limpopo. The ARC conducts research on Quelea population dynamics, migration and breeding patterns, and alternative and non-chemical control methods (Van der Walt 1999). They identify breeding and roosting sites; carry out ground control, nest destruction, and limited chemical control and liaise directly with farmers and local municipalities.

The red-billed Quelea are small, sparrow-like birds with bright red conical bills (Fig. 2). They are found throughout sub-Saharan Africa, from Senegal and Sudan to South Africa. They prefer open grasslands, savannas, and cultivated areas, often near water sources and avoid dense forests and high-altitude regions. They are highly nomadic, moving thousands of kilometres annually in response to rainfall and food availability. They are extremely gregarious and form massive flocks that move in synchronised patterns, creating spectacular “rolling clouds” in the sky and can number in the millions (Fig. 3). They roost in dense vegetation and breed in huge colonies, sometimes covering entire landscapes. Primarily granivorous, feeding on seeds of wild grasses, but when natural food is scarce, they raid cereal crops such as sorghum, millet, wheat, and rice. During breeding, they supplement their diet with insects (e.g., grasshopper nymphs, termites) for protein (Van der Walt, 1999).

The Springbok Flats is an extensive plain situated in Limpopo, South Africa. To the east, it includes the towns of Roedtan, Tuinplaas, and Settlers. The 80 km-wide and 130 km-long swaths of land are oriented in a northeasterly direction. The plain, which is exceptionally flat and situated at an altitude of 1,000 m above sea level, experiences warm summers (shielded from cold winds by surrounding uplands) and dry winters. An annual rainfall of about 620 mm is the norm. It is considered a highly fertile thornveld–grassland area (Mucina & Rutherford, 2006).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Surveys were undertaken on the Springbok Flats (SF) by members of ARC-Plant Health and Protection, to determine the effect of control methods of the red-billed quelea on invertebrates such as spiders, and the sampled material was sorted and identified at the National Collection of Arachnida (Van den Berg *et al.*, 2002).

Figures 1–3. 1. The thornveld–grassland of the Springbok Flats. 2. Male red-billed quelea. 3. Swarm of birds causing damage to crops. Credits: Agricultural Research Council.

Study area: The surveys took place in the Springbok Flats, an extensive plain of fertile thornveld–grassland situated in the Waterberg District of the Limpopo (Mucina & Rutherford, 2006). Sampling took place on six farms stretching from Settlers, Roedtan to Naboomspruit: Roedtan (-24.60, 29.08); Tuinplaas (-24.89, 28.73); Settlers, Farm Bekendevelei (-24.60, 29.08); Settlers, Lodge (-25.01, 28.88); Settlers, Wildskamp (-24.60, 29.08); Settlers, Farm Tweekansen (-25.49, 28.57) (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. The area sampled on the Springbok Flats in the Limpopo Province.

Collecting methods: Spiders were sampled monthly using pitfall traps for ground fauna and beating and sweeping to sample vegetation (Figs 6 & 7).

Collecting period: The survey was conducted over 27 months, from January 2001 to March 2003.

Voucher specimens: All the material was sorted and identified in the National Collection of Arachnida (non-Acari) (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection. All the voucher specimens were deposited in the NCA.

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider Project (Foord *et al.*, 2020), the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures, new species, and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species known from only one sex, or known only from type locality, or species that could not be identified were listed as DD (data deficient).

Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were of least concern (LC); those of categories 3–5 are South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC.

Endemicity value: The endemicity values for each species sampled at the SF are provided in Table 3 & 4. Five endemicity categories are recognized:

- 5—species are only known from the type locality (Springbok Flats).
- 4—species known only from the Limpopo Province endemic (LE).
- 3—known from >three provinces, a South African endemic (SAE).
- 2—known from other countries in Southern Africa, endemic (STHE).
- 1—known from several countries in the Afrotropical Region, endemic (AE).
- 0—also known from outside the Afrotropical Region.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 6380 spiders represented by 245 species, 157 genera, from 38 families, were recorded from the SF (Tables 1 & 2). The SF survey forms part of the SANSA Limpopo survey project (Table 1). The spiders sampled at SF represent 27% of the 905 species recorded from Limpopo, and 40% of the 600 species recorded in the Waterberg District survey, and 10.8% of the South African species (Table 1).

Figures 5–7. Springbok Flats sampling 5. The habitat. 6. Beating the trees sampling spiders. 7. Pitfall traps to sample the ground dwellers.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity sampled from different sites in the Limpopo Province and South Africa.

AREA	FAM	GEN	SPP.	REFERENCE
South Africa	71	495	2265	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2023)
Limpopo	60	346	905	Foord <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Waterberg dist	54	292	600	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (in press)
Springbokflats	38	157	245	present

TABLE 2: Spider diversity of the Springbok Flats in the Limpopo Province with the total number of families, genera (G) and species (SP.)

FAMILIES	G	SP.	%	FAMILIES	G	SP.	%
Agelenidae	2	2	0.8	Oonopidae	2	3	1.2
Araneidae	16	28	11.4	Orsolobidae	1	1	0.4
Barychelidae	2	2	0.8	Oxyopidae	3	10	4.0
Caponiidae	1	1	0.4	Palpimanidae	2	2	0.8
Cheiracanthiidae	1	1	0.4	Philodromidae	5	7	2.9
Corinnidae	6	7	2.9	Pholcidae	1	2	0.8
Ctenidae	2	2	0.8	Pisauridae	3	3	1.2
Cyrtacheniidae	2	5	2.0	Prodidomidae	2	4	1.6
Dictynidae	3	3	1.2	Salticidae	16	28	11.4
Eresidae	2	2	0.8	Segestriidae	1	1	0.4
Gnaphosidae	17	42	17.1	Selenopidae	1	1	0.4
Hahniidae	1	1	0.4	Sicariidae	1	1	0.4
Hersiliidae	2	3	1.2	Sparassidae	3	3	1.2
Idiopidae	3	3	1.2	Theraphosidae	3	3	1.2
Linyphiidae	4	4	1.6	Theridiidae	7	10	4.0
Liocranidae	1	1	0.4	Thomisidae	15	24	9.8
Lycosidae	9	12	4.9	Trachelidae	4	4	1.6
Mimetidae	1	1	0.4	Uloboridae	1	1	0.4
Oecobiidae	1	1	0.4	Zodariidae	10	15	6.1
				157 245			

Family diversity: Of the 38 spider families collected from SF (Tables 2 & 4), the four most species-rich families are the Gnaphosidae (42 spp.), Salticidae and Araneidae, both with 28 spp., followed by the Thomisidae (24 spp.). Eleven families are represented by singletons. All the sampled specimens in the NCA are available for taxonomic research, and two SF species were described as new to science: *Fuchiba aquilonia* Haddad & Lyle, 2008 (Trachelidae) (Fig. 8), and *Zelotes songus* FitzPatrick, 2007 (Gnaphosidae) (Fig. 9)

TABLE 3: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at the Springbok Flats in the Waterberg District of the Limpopo Province.

CONSERVATION STATUS	NO. SPP.	%
Not evaluated NE	6	2.4
Data deficient DD	4	1.6
Least concern LC	235	95.9
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	21	8.7
1 – African endemics (AE)	109	44.5
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	60	24.5
3 – South African endemics (SAE)	45	18.4
4 – Limpopo endemics (LE)	5	0.8
5 – Type locality (Springbok Flats)	2	0.4

Conservation status: Six species from six families could not be identified to species level and were not evaluated (NE). (Tables 3 & 4). They belong to genera in the families Araneidae, Ctenidae, Dictynidae, Oonopidae and Oxyopidae that have not yet been revised in South Africa.

Of the four Data Deficient species, *Brachionopus tristis* (Purcell, 1903) (Theraphosidae), *Idiops gunningi* Hewitt, 1913 (Idiopidae) (Fig. 11), *Zelotes songus* (Gnaphosidae) (Fig. 9) and *Prodidomus simoni* Dalmás, 1919 (Prodidomidae) (Fig. 10) are known only from one sex, and they have a restricted distribution, so more information is needed to determine their status. Most species (95.9%) have a wide distribution and are of Least Concern.

Endemism: 21 species of SF (44.5%) have a wide African distribution, and 8.7% are also found in countries outside Africa. Sixty species (24.5%) are found in southern Africa; 55 species (22.5%) are endemic to South Africa; five are Limpopo endemics; and two are known only from the SF.

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Figures 8–11. 8. *Fuchiba aquilonia* (C. Haddad). 9. *Zelotes songus* (P. Webb). 10. *Prodidomus simoni* (V. vd Walt). 11. *Idiops gunningi* (Peter Webb).

Figures 12–26. Spiders of the Springbok Flats. 12. *Eriovixia excelsa*. 13. *Dresserus colsoni*. 14. *Haplodrassus stationis*. 15. *Zelotes frenchi*. 16. *Hogna spenceri*. 17. *Oxyopes schenkeli*. 18. *Thanatus dorsilineatus*. 19. *Hyllus brevitarsis*. 20. *Natta horizontalis*. 21. *Thyene inflata*. 22. *Thyene ogdeni*. 23. *Hewittia gracilis*. 24. *Thomisops sulcatus*. 25. *Xysticus fagei*. 26. *Orthobula radiata*. Credits: Peter Webb

TABLE 4: Spiders of the Springbok Flats listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CON), country endemism (CEN), LC Least Concern, DD Data Deficient, VU Vulnerable, NE Not Evaluated.

SPECIES	END	CON	CEN	SPECIES	END	CON	CEN
1. Family Agelenidae				8. Family Cyrtaucheniidae			
<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE	<i>Ancylotrypa brevipalpis</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Benoitia raymondeae</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE	<i>Ancylotrypa nuda</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE
2. Family Araneidae				<i>Ancylotrypa pretoriae</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Araneus apricus</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE	<i>Ancylotrypa rufescens</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Araneus coccinella</i> Pocock, 1898	3	LC	SAE	<i>Homostola zebrina</i> Purcell, 1902	2	LC	STHE
<i>Araneus nigroquadratus</i> Lawrence, 1937	2	LC	STHE	9. Family Dictynidae			
<i>Araneus</i> sp. (new)		NE		<i>Archaeodictyna conducta</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876)	0	LC	C
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE	<i>Dictyna</i> sp.		NE	
<i>Argiope lobata</i> (Pallas, 1772)	0	LC	C	<i>Mashimo leleupi</i> Lehtinen, 1967	1	LC	AE
<i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	10. Family Eresidae			
<i>Caerostris sexcupidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE	<i>Dresserus colsoni</i> Tucker, 1920 (Fig. 13)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Acantharachne seydeli</i> Giltay, 1935	1	LC	AE	<i>Stegodyphus mimosarum</i> Pavesi, 1883	1	LC	AE
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	11. Family Gnaphosidae			
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	<i>Ammozenus amphalodes</i> Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980	3	LC	SAE
<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889) (Fig. 12)	0	LC	C	<i>Aneplasa interrogationis</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C. L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE	<i>Aphantaulax inornata</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Hypsosinga holzaphelae</i> (Lessert, 1936)	3	LC	SAE	<i>Asemesthes ceresicola</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Isoxya cicatricosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE	<i>Asemesthes decoratus</i> Purcell, 1908	2	LC	STHE
<i>Isoxya tabulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	1	LC	AE	<i>Asemesthes flavipes</i> Purcell, 1908	2	LC	STHE
<i>Nemoscolus elongatus</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE	<i>Asemesthes paynteri</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	<i>Camillina maun</i> Platnick & Murphy, 1987	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	<i>Haplodrassus bechuanicus</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE	<i>Haplodrassus helenae</i> (Purcell, 1907)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Neoscona theisi theisiella</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE	<i>Haplodrassus lophognathus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	1	LC	AE	<i>Haplodrassus splendens</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	<i>Haplodrassus stationis</i> (Tucker, 1923) (Fig. 14)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Pararaneus spectator</i> (Karsch, 1885)	0	LC	C	<i>Ibala arcus</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	<i>Leptopilos vasivulva</i> Haddad & Booyesen, 2022	2	LC	STHE
<i>Singa albodorsata</i> Kauri, 1950	3	LC	SAE	<i>Megamyrmaekion transvaalense</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Micaria bispicula</i> Booyesen & Haddad, 2021	2	LC	STHE
3. Family Barychelidae				<i>Nomisia varia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pisenor arcturus</i> (Tucker, 1917)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Pterotracha auris</i> (Tucker, 1923)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Sipalolasma humicola</i> (Benoit, 1965)	1	LC	AE	<i>Rastellus kariba</i> Platnick & Griffin, 1990	2	LC	STHE
4. Family Caponiidae				<i>Setaphis browni</i> (Tucker, 1923)	0	LC	C
<i>Caponia chelifera</i> Lessert, 1936	2	LC	STHE	<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C
5. Family Cheiracanthiidae				<i>Trachyzelotes jaxartensis</i> (Kroneberg, 1875)	0	LC	C
<i>Cheiracanthium vansonii</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE	<i>Xerophaeus aurariarum</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
6. Family Corinnidae				<i>Xerophaeus lunulifer</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
<i>Cambalida dippenaarae</i> Haddad, 2012	1	LC	AE	<i>Xerophaeus patricki</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
<i>Cambalida fulvipes</i> (Simon, 1896)	1	LC	AE	<i>Xerophaeus vickermani</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Coenoptychus mutillicus</i> (Haddad, 2004)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes aridus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
<i>Copa flavoplumosa</i> Simon, 1886	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes corrugatus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
<i>Copuetta lacustris</i> (Strand, 1916)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes frenchi</i> Tucker, 1923 (Fig. 15)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Corinnomma semiglabrum</i> (Simon, 1896)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes fuliginous</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pronophaea proxima</i> Lessert, 1923	3	LC	SAE	<i>Zelotes humilis</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
7. Family Ctenidae				<i>Zelotes lavus</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Anahita</i> sp.		NE		<i>Zelotes natalensis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Ctenus transvaalensis</i> Benoit, 1981	3	LC	SAE				

SPECIES	END	CON	CEN
<i>Zelotes otavi</i> Fitzpatrick, 2007	2	LC	STHE
<i>Zelotes reduncus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Zelotes sclateri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1872)	1	LC	AE
<i>Zelotes songus</i> FitzPatrick, 2007 (Fig. 9)	5	DD	LE
<i>Zelotes tuckeri</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
<i>Zelotes zonognathus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
12. Family Hahniidae			
<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
13. Family Hersiliidae			
<i>Hersilia sericea</i> Pocock, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Hersilia setifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	2	LC	STHE
<i>Tyrotama australis</i> (Simon, 1893)	2	LC	STHE
14. Family Idiopidae			
<i>Ctenolophus fenoulheti</i> Hewitt, 1913	3	LC	SAE
<i>Idiops gunningi</i> Hewitt, 1913 (Fig. 11)	4	DD	SAE
<i>Segregara transvaalensis</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE
15. Family Linyphiidae			
<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE
<i>Metaleptyphantus perexiguus</i> (Simon & Ostearius melanopygius (O. P.-Cambridge, 1879)	1	LC	AE
<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O. P.-Cambridge, 1879)	0	LC	C
<i>Pelecopsis janus</i> Jocqué, 1984	2	LC	STHE
16. Family Liocranidae			
<i>Rhaeboctesis transvaalensis</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE
17. Family Lycosidae			
<i>Allocosa exserta</i> Roewer, 1959	2	LC	STHE
<i>Allocosa lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1951)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Hippasa australis</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
<i>Hippasosa guttata</i> (Karsch, 1878)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hogna spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1898) (Fig. 16)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pardosa umtalica</i> Purcell, 1903	1	LC	AE
<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Proevippa fascicularis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
<i>Wadicosa oncka</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
18. Family Macrobonidae			
<i>Chresiona invalida</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
19. Family Mimetidae			
<i>Anansi natalensis</i> (Lawrence, 1938)	3	LC	SAE
20. Family Oecobiidae			
<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C
21. Family Oonopidae			
<i>Gamasomorpha australis</i> Hewitt, 1915	3	LC	SAE
<i>Gamasomorpha humicola</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE
<i>Orchestina</i> sp.		NE	
22. Family Orsolobidae			
<i>Azania lobus lawrencei</i> Griswold & Platnick, 1987	2	LC	STHE
23. Family Oxyopidae			
<i>Hamataliwa fronticornis</i> (Lessert, 1927)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hamataliwa kulczynskii</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE

SPECIES	END	CON	CEN
<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE
<i>Oxyopes pallidicoloratus</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes russoi</i> Caporiacco, 1940	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes schenkeli</i> Lessert, 1927 (Fig. 17)	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. 3		NE	
<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
24. Family Palpimanidae			
<i>Diaphorocellus biplagiatus</i> Simon, 1893	2	LC	STHE
<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
25. Family Philodromidae			
<i>Hirriusa variegata</i> (Simon, 1895)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Philodromus bigibbus australis</i> Lawrence, 1928	3	LC	SAE
<i>Philodromus guineensis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Suemus punctatus</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE
<i>Thanatus dorsilineatus</i> Jézéquel, 1964 (Fig. 18)	1	LC	AE
<i>Tibellus hollidayi</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE
<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
26. Family Pholcidae			
<i>Smeringopus atomarius</i> Simon, 1910	2	LC	STHE
<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
27. Family Pisauridae			
<i>Euprostenops australis</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Perenethis simoni</i> (Lessert, 1916)	1	LC	AE
<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
28. Family Prodidomidae			
<i>Prodidomus simoni</i> Dalmas, 1919 (Fig. 10)	6	DD	SFE
<i>Theuma ababensis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Theuma fusca</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
<i>Theuma purcelli</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
29. Family Salticidae			
<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Cyryba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE
<i>Evarcha alba</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Evarcha flagellaris</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	1	LC	AE
<i>Evarcha ignea</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
<i>Helafricanus debilis</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hispo georgius</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1892)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hyllus argyrotroxus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Hyllus brevitaris</i> Simon, 1902 (Fig. 19)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hyllus dotatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
<i>Langona hirsuta</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
<i>Mogrus mathisi</i> (Berland & Millot, 1941)	0	LC	C
<i>Natta chionogaster</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879 (Fig. 20)	1	LC	AE
<i>Nigorella hirsuta</i> Wesolowska, 2009	2	LC	STHE
<i>Phlegra karoo</i> Wesolowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE
<i>Phlegra pusilla</i> Wesolowska & van Harten, 1994	1	LC	AE
<i>Phlegra simplex</i> Wesolowska & Russell-Smith, 2000	1	LC	AE

SPECIES	END	CON	CEN
<i>Phlegra pusilla</i> Wesotowska & van Harten, 1994	1	LC	AE
<i>Pignus simoni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Stenaelurillus guttiger</i> (Simon, 1901)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Stenaelurillus termitophagus</i> (Wesotowska & Cumming, 1999)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873) (Fig. 21)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene ogdeni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903 (Fig. 22)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene semiargentea</i> (Simon, 1884)	1	LC	AE
<i>Trapezocephalus lesserti</i> (Wesotowska, 1986)	1	LC	AE
<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE
30. Family Segestriidae			
<i>Ariadna corticola</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE
31. Family Selenopidae			
<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	1	LC	AE
32. Family Sicariidae			
<i>Loxosceles simillima</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
33. Family Sparassidae			
<i>Eusparassus jaegeri</i> Moradmand, 2013	2	LC	STHE
<i>Olios sjostedti</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
<i>Pseudomicrommata longipes</i> (Bösenberg & Lenz, 1895)	1	LC	AE
34. Family Theraphosidae			
<i>Brachionopus tristis</i> Purcell, 1903	4	DD	SAE
<i>Ceratogyrus darlingi</i> Pocock, 1897	2	LC	STHE
<i>Idiothele nigrofulva</i> (Pocock, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
35. Family Theridiidae			
<i>Emertonella episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Phoroncidia eburnea</i> (Simon, 1895)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
<i>Steatoda triangulosa</i> (Walckenaer, 1802)	3	LC	AE
<i>Theridion pictum</i> (Walckenaer, 1802)	0	LC	C
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Tidarren cuneolatum</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
36. Family Thomisidae			
<i>Ansiea tuckeri</i> (Lessert, 1919)	1	LC	AE
<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
<i>Hewittia gracilis</i> Lessert, 1928 (Fig. 23)	1	LC	AE
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses paradoxus</i> (Lucas, 1846)	0	LC	C
<i>Monaeses quadrituberculatus</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
<i>Ozyptila caenosa</i> Jézéquel, 1966	1	LC	AE
<i>Parasmodix quadrituberculata</i> Jézéquel, 1966	1	LC	AE
<i>Pherecydes lucinae</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980	3	LC	SAE
<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C
<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
<i>Stiphropus affinis</i> Lessert, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Stiphropus bisigillatus</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Synema nigrotibiale</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Synema vallonitoni</i> Lessert, 1923	2	LC	STHE

SPECIES	END	CON	CEN
<i>Thomisops sulcatus</i> Simon, 1895 (Fig. 24)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus comellinii</i> Garcia-Neto, 1989	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Xysticus fagei</i> Lessert, 1919 (Fig. 25)	1	LC	AE
<i>Xysticus mulleri</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
37. Family Trachelidae			
<i>Afrocecto plana</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2010	1	LC	AE
<i>Fuchiba aquilonia</i> Haddad & Lyle, 2008 (Fig. 26)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Orthobula radiata</i> Simon, 1897 (Fig. 26)	1	LC	AE
<i>Trachelas pusillus</i> Lessert, 1923	1	LC	AE
38. Family Uloboridae			
<i>Miagrammopes longicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE
39. Family Zodariidae			
<i>Caesetius inflatus</i> Jocqué, 1991	1	LC	AE
<i>Capheris decorata</i> Simon, 1904	1	LC	AE
<i>Capheris subtilis</i> Jocqué, 2009	2	LC	STHE
<i>Chariobas cylindraceus</i> Simon, 1893	1	LC	AE
<i>Chariobas cylindraceus</i> Simon, 1893	1	LC	AE
<i>Cydrela schoemanae</i> Jocqué, 1991	3	LC	SAE
<i>Diores annetteae</i> Jocqué, 1990	3	LC	SAE
<i>Diores recurvatus</i> Jocqué, 1990	2	LC	STHE
<i>Diores magicus</i> Jocqué & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1992	2	LC	STHE
<i>Diores triarmatus</i> Lessert, 1929	1	LC	AE
<i>Heradida bicincta</i> Simon, 1910	2	LC	STHE
<i>Microdiores</i> sp.		NE	
<i>Palfuria spirembolus</i> Szűts & Jocqué, 2001	2	LC	STHE
<i>Ranops robinae</i> Jocqué & Henrard, 2020	3	LC	SAE
<i>Systemoplacis vandami</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE

A first look at the non-acarine arachnid biodiversity of the Meerkat National Park, South Africa

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ABSTRACT: In this study, we present the first preliminary checklist of the non-acarine arachnids of the Meerkat National Park, based on iNaturalist images generated during a BioBlitz conducted in the park in October 2024 and an Entomology field excursion conducted by the University of the Free State in March - April 2025 in the Jaskloof area. During the latter, sampling was conducted in three biotopes (open Nama Karoo grassland, a rocky hillside and riparian woodland) using a standardized sampling protocol (beating, sweeping and pitfalls), supplemented by ad hoc collecting by beating, hand collecting from rocks, litter sifting and night collecting. A total of 89 spider species in 30 families were recorded, as well as six species of scorpions, four species of solifuges and two species of pseudoscorpions. The most species-rich families sampled were Salticidae (15 spp.) and Gnaphosidae (14 spp.). We also generated 33 DNA barcodes representing 22 species based on the material collected, all of which are imaged. All of the species identified to species level (60 spp.) can be considered of Least Concern. The majority of them are southern African endemics (31 spp.), whereas 10 are South African endemics, 13 Afrotropical endemics and six species are cosmopolitan. Although this is only a preliminary survey carried out in a small portion in the west of the park, it provides valuable baseline data to guide future sampling efforts and species identifications.

INTRODUCTION

The South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) has made a massive effort during the last three decades to improve sample coverage of non-acarine arachnids in the country, with a particular focus on identifying gaps in sampling effort and addressing them through targeted sampling (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). This effort, largely driven by the development and application of the standardized SANSa rapid sampling protocol (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2015), was largely focused in the eastern and central parts of the country, while the arid and semi-arid western half remained poorly sampled (Janion-Scheepers *et al.*, 2016; Foord *et al.*, 2020; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023; Van der Mescht *et al.*, 2024), a situation that continues to persist.

One of the specific aims of SANSa was to sample and provide baseline data on the South African National Parks (SANParks, #DIPSA 1296). Although a few parks were well sampled and the results published prior to the completion of SANSa phases I and II, most of the 19 parks did not have a comprehensive checklist of the non-acarine arachnid fauna until recently (see Haddad *et al.*, 2025). Despite this progress, several parks remain undersampled and two, Meerkat and Camdeboo, have no spider records at all. Considering the significance of SANParks to conservation in South Africa, it is essential that data be generated for those parks for which no checklists are available.

During March-April 2025, the 3rd year Entomology students at the University of the Free State (UFS) undertook the annual student field excursion to the previously unsampled Meerkat National Park (MNP) near Carnarvon in the karoo. MNP is South Africa's most recently proclaimed national park (March 2020), which was an effort to offset the impact of the Square Kilometer Array (SKA) telescope system on the environment. Initially, a Bioblitz in the MNP was held in October 2024 but could not be attended by the authors, which resulted in the excursion being held there to facilitate sampling of non-acarine arachnids. The primary objective was to provide baseline biodiversity data on arthropods, focusing on insects and non-acarine arachnids.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was undertaken in the MNP in the Upper Karoo and Bushmanland area, with the nearest towns being Carnarvon, Williston, Sakrivier, Brandvlei and Vanwyksvlei. Topographically, the region is characterized by continuous and isolated flat-topped mesas separated by open plains. The area experiences cold winters and very hot summers, with most of the rainfall falling during late summer. For more details of the MNP geology and vegetation, see Van Rooyen & Van Rooyen (2022).

To effectively sample arthropods, a variety of sampling methods are required to collect in different habitat strata. This not only allows for better characterization of assemblages occupying different microhabitats within each biotope but enables comparisons between strata within a biotope and within-stratum differences between biotopes (as presented in the student reports). The UFS Entomology students were divided into three groups that replicated a rapid sampling protocol (Haddad, 2021) in the three biotopes sampled, an open Nama Karoo grassland (Fig. 1A), a riparian woodland (Fig. 1B) and a northwest-facing rocky hillside (Fig. 1C), all in the Jaskloof area along the western margin of the MNP. However, leaf litter was sparse in two of the three biotopes, so litter sifting was replaced with sweep-netting as a sampling method. Due to logistical constraints, no sampling could be conducted in the eastern section of the park in the proximity of the SKA, which is dominated by open gravel plains (Fig. 1D).

Each group took 10 samples of vegetation beating (50 beats each), 10 pitfall traps left out for four days, and 10 samples of sweep-netting vegetation (50 sweeps each), which was replicated in each of the three biotopes. Additional collecting was conducted by the authors by beating, hand collecting under rocks, leaf litter sifting and night collecting around Jaskloof (Fig. 1E-F). We also set up a light trap for the students to collect nocturnal insects on four of the nights, where any visiting arachnids were collected. C.H. sorted and identified all the spiders and other arachnids for the students so that the data could be included in their reports. Material has been deposited in the National Museum in Bloemfontein (spiders and pseudoscorpions), American Museum of Natural History in New York (scorpions) and Ditsong National Museum of Natural History in Pretoria (solifuges).

Figure 1. Biotopes in the Meerkat National Park. A Open plain with Nama Karoo grassland, Jaskloof; B Northwest-facing hillside, Jaskloof; C Hillside and riparian woodland, Jaskloof; D Open gravel plain near park entrance, with the SKA in the background; E Jaskloof farmhouse and outbuildings, with hillsides and riparian woodland; F Farm dam at Jaskloof. Photos: A N. Zulu; B–F C. Haddad.

In addition, DNA barcodes (cytochrome *c* oxidase subunit I, COI) were generated for 33 spider specimens from the park (Appendix 1). The plates were submitted to the Canadian Centre for DNA Barcoding and all sequence data is publicly accessible on the SPIZA project on BOLD (www.boldsystems.org). Some of the arthropods collected were photographed by Ruan Booysen and Rudolph Steenkamp and the images and data have been uploaded to iNaturalist, to supplement images taken during the Bioblitz in October 2024.

For each species in the checklist (Appendix 1), we present an indication of the Red List conservation status (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). The species sampled were all considered Least Concern (LC), except for those only identified to genus level, which were not evaluated (NE); no species belonged to any of the threat categories. The endemicity index was also provided for each species, including the following applicable categories: SAE – South African endemic; STHE – Southern African endemic (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers); AE – endemic to the Afrotropical Region; C – cosmopolitan.

RESULTS

Altogether, 89 spider species in 30 families were collected, together with six species of scorpions, four species of solifuges and two species of pseudoscorpions (Appendix 1). Of these, seven species were recorded during the BioBlitz of October 2024 and are known from photographic records on iNaturalist only; the remaining species were collected from voucher specimens during surveys in March 2025, although some were previously also recorded on iNaturalist or added following the survey (Appendix 1).

Images of some of the commonly collected species are presented in Fig. 2. *Thysanina gracilis* (Trachelidae, Fig. 2A), juveniles of an unidentified *Dendryphantus* sp. (Salticidae, Fig. 2H) and various Philodromidae and Oxyopidae were abundant in beating samples in all three biotopes. Species commonly collected from under rocks on the hillsides and in the riparian woodland included *Ibala bilinearis* (Gnaphosidae, Fig. 2B), a new *Pseudauximus* sp. (Macrobonidae, Fig. 2C), a new *Scytodes* sp. (Scytodidae, Fig. 2D), *Prodidomus purpurascens* (Prodidomidae, Fig. 2E), a likely new *Quamtana* sp. (Pholcidae) and a new *Euophrys* sp. (Salticidae, Fig. 2J). Only a single *Hexophthalma hahni* (Sicariidae, Fig. 2F) adult female and juvenile *Harpactira* sp. (Theraphosidae, Fig. 2I) were collected under rocks around the Jaskloof residence. Common in sweep-netting samples were *Argiope australis* (Araneidae) in the open plain and various Philodromidae in all three biotopes.

Paradonea variegata (Eresidae, Fig. 2G) males were active on the soils surface in the late afternoon, whereas females were collected from their cribellate retreat-webs constructed beneath large rocks in the riparian woodland, open plains and hillsides, particularly around the Jaskloof homestead. Males of this species mimic *Camponotus fulvopilosus* ants, which are common in the park. Two myrmecophilous species, *Mexcala rufa* (Salticidae) and *Stiphropus affinis* (Thomisidae, Fig. 2K) were commonly found around *C. fulvopilosus* nests near Jaskloof and are likely widespread in the park. Although the new *Cydrela* sp. (Zodariidae) also clearly has similar colouration to *C. fulvopilosus*, it was only collected in pitfall traps.

The rapid sampling protocol used was relatively ineffective in sampling large numbers of spiders, and both numbers and species richness per sample were markedly lower than when the protocol was used in the western Free State, in the transition zone between the Nama Karoo and Grassland biomes (Haddad, 2021). Generally, beating sampled the highest abundance and species richness in all

three biotopes, although the hillside consistently performed poorest for both metrics for all three methods used. Often, only one or two spiders were collected per sample, explaining why the abundance and species richness per sample were very similar at all biotope-method combinations (Fig. 3).

The 33 specimens submitted for DNA barcoding represent 22 species (Appendix 1; Fig. 4). This includes the first DNA barcodes in the SPIZA project for *Caponia spiralifera*, *Camillina pavesii*, *Setaphis browni*, *Pseudauximus* sp.*, *Theuma schreineri*, *Helafricanus* sp.*, *Euophrys* sp.*, *Stiphropus affinis* and *Caesetius* sp.* (* indicates new species).

DISCUSSION

Through our efforts, we were able to generate a meaningful baseline dataset on non-acarine biodiversity in the MNP, which will hopefully stimulate research there in the future. As this was only a preliminary biodiversity assessment with very limited geographical scope in the park and only carried out over the course of one week, it would be premature to make any management recommendations. Nonetheless, valuable data has been provided to facilitate future ecological and conservation work in the park.

It is worth mentioning that several new taxa were collected during our study, including species of *Ammoxenus* (Gnaphosidae), *Pseudauximus*, *Euophrys* and *Helafricanus*, *Scytodes* and *Caesetius*, as well as a likely new species of the insect order Mantophasmatodea. Further new species may belong to taxonomically poorly studied spider families that could only be identified to genus level. For the orders Solifugae and Pseudoscorpiones, specialist identifications following more detailed study are necessary to confirm the identity of the species sampled. For example, only female solifuges were sampled for two species, and males are required for accurate species identification based on the flagellum structure. Four species of solifuges have been recorded from the Carnarvon area (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2006), which may help narrow down the species likely to occur in the MNP.

During a relatively short period of one week, we were able to generate a sizable dataset on the arthropods occurring in the vicinity of Jaskloof. Although this was only baseline biodiversity survey, it has enabled us to familiarize ourselves with the landscape and facilities in the park and to generate a lot of material that will be valuable for taxonomic study, studies of predation biology and DNA barcoding. We hope to visit again in the future and explore the area and its biodiversity further.

All the species identified to species level are considered Least Concern according to their current South African Spider Red List scores (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). In evaluating the global distribution of all the species sampled, six are cosmopolitan, 13 have a broad distribution in the Afrotropical Region and 10 are South African endemics. The majority of species identified to species level are southern African endemics (31 spp.), usually with distributions extending into Namibia and sometimes other southern African countries. A further 41 species could only be identified to genus level and would need to be evaluated once they are (re)described or adult specimens have been collected. It is plausible that some of them may be of conservation concern.

The MNP remains largely unexplored with regards to its arthropod biodiversity, with most of the park aside from Jaskloof never having been sampled before. Future efforts to collect in other areas could be facilitated by the upgrade of the old farmhouses and other accommodation sources, which will improve accessibility and logistics. We look forward to the proposed changes and having the possibility to sample this unique Nama Karoo landscape again in the future and provide data on the arthropod fauna.

Figure 2. Habitus photographs of several live Arachnida collected in the Meerkat National Park: A *Thysanina gracilis* (Trachelidae); B *Ibala bilinearis* (Gnaphosidae); C *Pseudauximus* sp. (Macrobnidae); D *Scytodes* sp. (Scytodidae); E *Prodidomus purpurascens* (Prodidomidae); F *Hexophthalma hahni* (Sicariidae); G *Paradonea variegata* (Eresidae); H *Dendryphantes* sp. (Salticidae); I *Harpactira* sp. (Theraphosidae); J *Euophrys* sp. (Salticidae); K *Stiphropus affinis* (Thomisidae); L *Faella* sp. (Feaellidae); M *Nanolpium* sp. (Hesperolpiidae); N *Uroplectes gracilior* (Buthidae); O *Parabuthus schlechteri* (Buthidae); P *Opisthophthalmus karrooensis* (Scorpionidae); Q *Karasbergia methueni* (Buthidae); R *Blossia* sp. (Daesiidae). Photos: R. Booysen.

Figure 3. Mean \pm SD of spider abundance (A) and species richness (B) per sample collected by student groups in the Meerkat National Park. Abbreviations: NK – Nama Karoo veld; HI – Hillside; RW – Riparian woodland; B – beating vegetation; S – sweep-netting vegetation; P – pitfalls.

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Figure 4. Spider species from Meerkat National Park submitted for DNA barcoding: A *Caponia spiralisfera*, male (Caponiidae); B, C *Paradonea variegata*, male (B) and female (C) (Eresidae); D *Camillina pavesii*, male (Gnaphosidae); E *Ibalia bilinearis*, female (Gnaphosidae); F *Setaphis browni*, female (Gnaphosidae); G *Pseudauximus* sp., male (Macrobunidae); H *Diaphorocellus biplagiatus*, male (Palpimanidae); I, J *Palpimanus* sp., female (I) and male (J) (Palpimanidae); K, L *Prodidomus purpurascens*, male (K) and female (L) (Prodidomidae); M *Theuma schreineri*, female (Prodidomidae); N, O *Philodromus otjimbombe*, male (N) and female (O) (Philodromidae); P, Q *Euophrys* sp., male (P) and female (Q) (Salticidae); R *Helafricanus prozysniskii*, female (Salticidae); S *H. trepidus*, male; T, U *Helafricanus* sp., male (T) and female (U); V *Evarcha villosa*, male (Salticidae); W *Hexophthalma hahni*, female (Sicariidae); X, Y *Stiphropus affinis*, male (X) and female (Y) (Thomisidae); Z *Xysticus sagittifer*, female (Thomisidae); AA–CC *Thysanina gracilis*, males (Trachelidae), showing variation in cheliceral length; DD *Afroceca africana*, female (Trachelidae); EE, FF *Caesetius* sp., males (Zodariidae). Photos: C. Haddad.

Appendix 1. List of the non-acarine arachnids recorded from the Meerkat National Park, South Africa. Asterisks indicate new species. Abbreviations: Con – conservation status; End – endemism; NK – Nama Karoo grassland; HI – hillside; RW – riparian woodland; Barc – species submitted for DNA barcoding (cytochrome c oxidase subunit I); iNat – iNaturalist record. Conservation status: LC – Least Concern; NE – Not Evaluated. Endemicity index: AE – endemic to the Afrotropical Region; C – cosmopolitan; SAE – South African endemic; STHE – Southern African endemic (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers).

Family	Species	Con	End	NK	HI	RW	Barc	iNat
ARANEAE								
Agelenidae	sp. indet.	NE	–					X
Araneidae	<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	LC	AE	X	X	X		X
	<i>Larinioides</i> sp.	NE	–			X		
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	LC	C	X		X		
Caponiidae	<i>Caponia spiralis</i> Purcell, 1904	LC	SAE		X		X	
Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiramiona</i> sp.	NE	–	X	X	X		X
Eresidae	<i>Gandanameno</i> sp.	NE	–					X
	<i>Paradonea variegata</i> (Purcell, 1904)	LC	STHE		X		X	X
	<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898	LC	STHE					X
	<i>Stegodyphus tentoriicola</i> Purcell, 1904	LC	STHE	X				X
Gnaphosidae	<i>Ammoxenus coccineus</i> Simon, 1893	LC	STHE	X				
	<i>Ammoxenus</i> sp.*	NE	–		X			
	<i>Asemesthes albobittatus</i> Purcell, 1908	LC	STHE	X		X		
	<i>Asemesthes reflexus</i> Tucker, 1923	LC	SAE	X		X		
	<i>Camillina pavesii</i> (Simon, 1897)	LC	AE		X		X	
	<i>Camillina</i> sp. 2	NE	–			X		
	<i>Ibala bilinearis</i> (Tucker, 1923)	LC	STHE	X	X		X	X
	<i>Micaria</i> sp.	NE	–					X
	<i>Setaphis browni</i> (Tucker, 1923)	LC	C		X			
	<i>Xerophaeus</i> sp.	NE	–		X			X
	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	LC	AE			X		
	<i>Zelotes lavus</i> Tucker, 1923	LC	STHE			X		
	<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1872)	LC	AE			X		
Hersiliidae	<i>Tyrotama</i> sp.	NE	–		X			X
Linyphiidae	<i>Metaleptyphantus</i> sp.	NE	–	X		X		
	<i>Pelecopsis janus</i> Jocqué, 1984	LC	STHE	X	X	X		
	<i>Pelecopsis</i> sp. 2	NE	–		X			
	sp. indet.	NE	–			X		
Liocranidae	<i>Rhaeboctesis</i> sp. imm.	NE	–		X			X
Lycosidae	<i>Arctosa promontorii</i> (Purcell, 1900)	LC	SAE		X	X		
	<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	LC	STHE		X			
	<i>Hogna</i> sp.	NE	–			X		X
	<i>Proevippa</i> sp.	NE	–		X	X		X
Macrobnidae	<i>Pseudauximus</i> sp.*	NE	–		X		X	X
Oecobiidae	<i>Oecobius putus</i> O. P.-Cambridge, 1876	LC	C		X			X
Oxyopidae	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	LC	AE	X	X	X		X
	<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. 2	NE	–	X				X
	<i>Peucetia striata</i> Karsch, 1878	LC	AE		X			
	<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1896	LC	AE			X		X
Palpimanidae	<i>Diaphorocellus biplagiatus</i> Simon, 1893	LC	STHE		X	X	X	X
	<i>Palpimanus</i> sp.	NE	–		X		X	X
Philodromidae	<i>Hirriusa arenacea</i> (Lawrence, 1927)	LC	STHE	X				
	<i>Philodromus grosi</i> Lessert, 1943	LC	AE		X	X		
	<i>Philodromus otjimbumbé</i> Lawrence, 1927	LC	STHE	X	X	X	X	
	<i>Philodromus</i> sp. 3	NE	–	X			X	
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	LC	C			X		

Family	Species	Con	End	NK	HI	RW	Barc	iNat
Pholcidae	<i>Quamtana</i> sp.*	NE	–			X		
	<i>Smeringopus sederberg</i> Huber, 2012	LC	SAE		X	X		
Pisauridae	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	LC	AE	X		X		X
Prodidomidae	<i>Prodidomus purpurascens</i> Purcell, 1904	LC	SAE		X	X	X	X
	<i>Theuma schreineri</i> Purcell, 1907	LC	STHE	X				
	<i>Theuma</i> sp. 2	NE	–			X		
Salticidae	<i>Dendryphantas</i> sp. imm.	NE	–			X		X
	<i>Euophrys</i> sp.*	NE	–		X	X	X	X
	<i>Evarcha karas</i> Wesolowska, 2011	LC	STHE			X		
	<i>Evarcha villosa</i> Wesolowska & Haddad, 2018	LC	SAE			X	X	
	<i>Helafricanus prozysniskii</i> (Wesolowska, 2003)	LC	STHE			X	X	
	<i>Helafricanus trepidus</i> (Simon, 1910)	LC	STHE			X	X	
	<i>Helafricanus</i> sp.*	NE	–			X	X	
	<i>Icius insolitus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	LC	STHE	X	X	X		X
	<i>Langona hirsuta</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	LC	SAE			X		
	<i>Mexcala rufa</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	LC	STHE		X	X		X
	<i>Pellenes geniculatus</i> (Simon, 1868)	LC	C			X		
	<i>Pellenes tharinae</i> Wesolowska, 2006	LC	STHE	X				
	<i>Phlegra karoo</i> Wesolowska, 2006	LC	STHE		X	X		
	<i>Psenec dependens</i> (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011)	LC	SAE	X				
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	LC	AE	X		X		
Scytodidae	<i>Scytodes</i> sp.*	NE	–		X			X
Segestriidae	<i>Ariadna</i> sp.	NE	–		X			
Selenopidae	<i>Anyphops</i> sp. imm.	NE	–		X	X		X
Sicariidae	<i>Hexophtalma hahni</i> (Karsch, 1878)	LC	STHE			X	X	X
Sparassidae	<i>Olios correvoni</i> Lessert, 1921	LC	AE			X		
Tetragnathidae	<i>Tetragnatha</i> sp.	NE	–			X		
Theraphosidae	<i>Harpactira</i> sp.	NE	–			X		X
Theridiidae	<i>Achaearanea</i> sp.	NE	–			X		
	<i>Chryso</i> sp. imm.	NE	–			X		X
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	LC	C			X		X
	<i>Steatoda</i> sp. imm.	NE	–			X		X
	<i>Theridion</i> sp.	NE	–			X		
Thomisidae	<i>Ansiae</i> sp.	NE	–	X	X			
	<i>Heriaeus zanii</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	LC	SAE		X	X		X
	<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	LC	AE	X				
	<i>Stiphropus affinis</i> Lessert, 1923	LC	STHE		X	X	X	X
	<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	LC	AE			X		X
	<i>Thomisus</i> sp. 2	NE	–			X		
	<i>Xysticus sagittifer</i> Lawrence, 1927	LC	STHE		X		X	
Trachelidae	<i>Afroceto africana</i> (Simon, 1910)	LC	STHE	X			X	
	<i>Thysanina gracilis</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2006	LC	STHE	X	X	X	X	
Zodariidae	<i>Caesetius</i> sp.*	NE	–	X			X	
SCORPIONES								
Buthidae	<i>Karasbergia methueni</i> Hewitt, 1913	LC	STHE	X	X	X		X
	<i>Parabuthus capensis</i> (Ehrenberg, 1831)	LC	STHE					X
	<i>Parabuthus schlechteri</i> Purcell, 1899	LC	STHE	X				X
	<i>Uroplectes gracilior</i> Hewitt, 1914	LC	STHE	X	X	X		X

Family	Species	Con	End	NK	HI	RW	Barc	iNat
Scorpionidae	<i>Opisthophthalmus carinatus</i> (Peters, 1861)	LC	STHE					X
	<i>Opisthophthalmus karrooensis</i> Purcell, 1898	LC	SAE	X	X			X
PSEUDOSCORPIONES								
Feaellidae	<i>Feaella</i> sp.	NE	–					
Hesperolpiidae	<i>Nanolpium</i> sp.	NE	–		X			X
					X	X		X
SOLIFUGAE								
Daesiidae	<i>Biton</i> sp.	NE	–					
	<i>Blossia</i> sp.	NE	–	X				X
Solpugidae	<i>Solpugiba lineata</i> (C. L. Koch, 1842)	LC	STHE	X				X
	<i>Zeriassa</i> sp.	NE	–			X		X
								X

Key to the Harvestmen genera (Opiliones) of South Africa

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1. Odoriferous gland opening on conical tubercle dorsal on carapace (a); genital opening exposed, not covered by operculum (b) **Suborder CYPHOPHTHALMI**

- Opening of the odoriferous glands not situated on a tubercle but at the sides of the carapace (c); genital opening covered by a movable operculum (d) **2**

2. Terminal segment of tarsi I - II with 1 simple claw, tarsi III - IV with 2 claws or trifurcate claw **Suborder LANIATORES**

- Terminal segments of all tarsi with 1 simple claw **Suborder EUPNOI**

Suborder CYPHOPHTHALMI

Fam. PETTALIDAE

1. Odoriferous glands about 6 times as far from each other as from lateral edge of carapace; tergites closely covered with bead-like granules ***Parapurcellia* & *Purcellia***
 - Eyes absent ***Parapurcellia***
 - Eyes present at base of odofores ***Purcellia***
- Odoriferous glands 2-3 times as far from each other as from lateral edge of carapace; tergites smooth or with few small granules ***Purcellia argasiformis***

Suborder LANIATORES

- 1. Eyes separated (e)..... **BIANTIDAE**
- Eyes close together (f)..... **2**

- 2. Tarsus III + IV with 1 trifurcate claw in adults, or 1 claw bearing a variable number of small lateral teeth in juveniles **TRIAENONYCHIDAE**
- Tarsus III + IV with 2 true claws, simple or serrated3
- 3. Tarsus III-IV with a pseudonychium **TRIONYXELLIDAE - Genus *Randilella***
- Tarsus III-IV without a pseudonychium **ASSAMIIDAE**

Fam. BIANIIDAE

- 1. Tarsus II with 4 segments ***Cryptobiantes protector***
- Tarsus II with 5 or more segments **2**
- 2. Tarsus II with more than 5 segments ***Biantessus***
- Tarsus II with 5 segments ***Metabiantes***

Fam. ASSAMIIDAE

- 1. Tarsus II with 5 segments ***Polycoryphus asper***
- Tarsus II with >6 segments ***Cryptopygoplus***

Fam. TRIAENONYCHIDAE

- 1. Shape of sternum long and thin (g) **TRIAENONYCHINAE**
- Shape of sternum more triangular and wider **ADAEINAE**

Subfam. TRIAENONYCHINAE

1. Inferior surface of pedipalp femur with a strip of fine granulation in the middle **2**
 - Inferior surface of pedipalp femur without a strip of fine granulation in the middle **12**
2. Tarsus I with 2 segments **3**
 - Tarsus I with 3 segments **5**
3. Chelicera II without stridulating organ ***Ceratontia***
 - Chelicera II with stridulating organ **4**
4. Tarsus II with 2 segments, metatarsus I calcaneus much shorter than astragalus
 ***Lispomontia coxidens***
 - Tarsus II with 3-4 segments, metatarsus I calcaneus at least half astragalus length ***Biacumontia***
5. Chelicera II on inside with stridulating organ **6**
 - Chelicera II on inside without stridulating organ (present in some *Amatola*) **7**
6. Tarsus II with 9 segments ***Lawrencella inermis***
 - Tarsus II with 6 segments ***Gunvorina spatulate***
7. Tarsus II with 3 segments ***Monomontia***
 - Tarsus II with more than 3 segments **8**
8. Tarsus II with 4 segments ***Austromontia***
 - Tarsus II with more than 4 segments **9**
9. Calcaneus of metatarsi I and II longer than astragalus ***Amatola* (part)**
 - Calcaneus of metatarsi I and II much shorter than astragalus **10**
10. Dorsal scute divided into areas by transverse grooves ***Rostromontia***
 - Dorsal scute not divided into areas by transverse grooves **11**
11. Anterior margin of carapace with a row of round club-shaped granules ***Amatola* (part)**
 - Anterior margin of carapace without a row of round club-shaped granules ***Micromontia flava***
12. Tarsus I with 3 segments **13**
 - Tarsus I with more than 3 segments **17**
13. Tarsus II with 5 segments ***Paramontia***
 - Tarsus II with more than 5 segments **14**
14. Ocular tubercle with a lengthened point or tooth **15**
 - Ocular tubercle without a lengthened point or tooth **16**
15. Granules behind and at sides of ocular tubercle arranged in rows forming a symmetrical pattern
 ***Graemontia***
 - Granules behind and at the sides of the ocular tubercle irregularly disposed ***Mensamontia***
16. At least femur I with 5 ventral teeth and 5 dorsal tubercles ***Planimontia goodnightorum***
 - Femurs I-IV without teeth ***Roewerania***
17. Tarsus I with 4 segments **18**
 - Tarsus I with 5 segments **19**
18. Coxae I with a very long anterior tooth, stigmata not visible ***Yulella natalensis***
 - Coxae I without a very long anterior tooth, stigmata visible ***Austronuncia***
19. Ocular tubercle with a single terminal spine ***Lizamontia***
 - Ocular tubercle rounded and low ***Speleomontia cavernicola***

Subfam. ADAEINAE

- 1. Sternum more or less pentagonal **2**
 - Sternum triangular **4**
- 2. Sternum broadly pentagonal in posterior half, a narrow parallel-sided rod forming its anterior half, stigmae exposed ***Paradaeum ratrayi***
 - Sternum without an anterior rod-like expansion, stigmae hidden **3**
- 3. Tarsus I with 4 segments, sternum more than twice as long as broad ***Larifuga***
 - Tarsus I with 5 segments, sternum less than twice as long as broad ***Montadaeum purcelli***
- 4. Tarsus I with 4 segments **5**
 - Tarsus I with 3 segments **7**
- 5. Sternum broadly triangular ***Cryptadaeum capense***
 - Sternum narrowly triangular **6**
- 6. Dorsal scute with long cylindrical granules. Tarsus II with 7-14 segments ***Adaeulum***
 - Dorsal scute with conical triangular granules. Tarsus II with 13-18 segments ***Larifugella***
- 7. Tarsus II with 4-5 segments ***Micradaeum rugosum***
 - Tarsus II with more than 6(8-11) segments **8**
- 8. Palp tarsus not longer than patella + tibia ***Adaeum***
 - Palp tarsus longer than patella + tibia ***Heteradaeum exiguum***

Suborder PALPATORES

- 1. Eyes enormous and ocularium occupies most of prosoma (h), leg II shorter than leg IV **CADIDAE – genus *Cadella***
 - Eyes and ocularium normal (i & j), leg II longer than leg IV **2**
- 2. Tarsus of pedipalp with distinct terminal claw, chelicerae with irregular small and large teeth **PHALANGIIDAE**
 - Tarsus of pedipalp with terminal claw minute or absent, chelicerae with small equal-sized teeth .. **NEOPILIONIDAE**

CADIDAE

PHALANGIIDAE

NEOPILIONIDAE

Fam. NEOPILIONIDAE

- 1. Dorsal angle between palp patella and tibia less than 180° ***Vibone vetusta***
 - Dorsal angle between palp patella and tibia more than 180° ***Neopilio***

Fam. PHALANGIIDAE

- 1. Cheliceral segment II swollen; triangular white mark on posterior abdomen ***Guruia africana***
 - Cheliceral segment II not swollen; whiteout triangular mark posterior on abdomen ***Rhampsinitus***

Images of the Opiliones families with some genera and species to illustrate some of the characters discussed.

Fam. ACROPSOPILIONIDAE

Caddella sp. From Malmesbury. Photo: Wessel Pretorius

Caddella sp. from Ceres. Photo: Arno van der Vyver

Caddella sp. from Cederberg. Photo: Cecile Roux

Fam. ASSAMIIDAE

Douglas Photo: Marianka vd Berg

Lekgalameetse NR Photo: Vicky Field

Lekgalameetse NR Photo: Peter Webb

Fam. BIANIIDAE

Metabiantus sp. from Chris Hahni. Photo: Ruan Booysen

Metabiantus sp. from Irene. Photo: Peter Webb

Metabiantus sp. from Mtunzini. Photo: Ricky Taylor

Metabiantus sp. from Hoedspruit. Photo: Wynand Uys

Fam. PETTALIDAE

Purcellia argasiformis from Cape Peninsula. Photo: Jess Worsley

Fam. PHALANGIIDAE

Rhampsinitus sp. from Silaka Nature Reserve
Photo: S. Gussmann

Rhampsinitus sp. from Dlinza Forest Photo:
Ant West

Rhampsinitus sp. from Kloof. Photo: Peter Webb

Fam. NEOPILIONIDAE

Neopilio inferi

Fam. TRIAENONYCHIDAE

Larifuga sp. from Uniondale. Photo: Joy Paton

Adaeum sp. from Uniondale. Photo: Joy Paton

Possible *Adaeum* sp. from Amathole. Photo:
Charles Haddad

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FURTHER READING

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